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D4.4 – V Labs User’s Handbook

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNR	Italian National Research Council
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CWP	Coordinating Working Party on Fishery Statistics
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
DIVAnd	Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions
D4Science	Data Infrastructure promoting Open Science (managed by CNR)
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FIRMS	Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HFR	High Frequency Radar
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
MFS	Mediterranean Forecasting System
MHW	Marine HeatWave
OA	Overlap Area
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OT	Overlap Time
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
SSC	Sea Surface Currents
SSI	Storm Severity Index or Indicator
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
SPARQL	Standard query language and protocol for Linked Open Data on the web or for RDF triplestores
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Keywords

EOSC; Virtual Labs; Big Data; Virtual Research Environment; Data infrastructures

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

By working closely with long-term EU marine data services (i.e., EMODnet, Copernicus), and research data infrastructures (i.e., EuroArgo, SeaDataNet, Ecotaxa and others), the collaborative Blue-Cloud 2026 project is offering to the marine community a state-of-the-art Virtual Research Environment designed to implement an incubator of new research ideas, models and services, supporting scientists and researchers in designing, testing, and evaluating innovative computational analytical flows that extract valuable knowledge from diverse datasets, while accelerating open science and collaborative research in ocean sustainability.

The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) offers a comprehensive environment for sharing data, tools, and knowledge, fostering innovation and discovery. The Blue-Cloud architecture is the technological foundation of the [EOSC Node | Digital Twin of the Ocean](#), the federated thematic node within the [EOSC Federation](#). The Blue-Cloud VRE adheres to the EOSC Interoperability Framework, supporting standard data formats, common metadata profiles, and controlled vocabularies. It shares common standards and policies aligned with the [EOSC Federation Handbook](#). By integrating advanced analytical tools, robust computing resources, and diverse datasets from observations and models, the platform empowers researchers to tackle complex ocean challenges and enhances the scientific community's ability to understand and predict marine phenomena while fostering the development of cutting-edge technologies and methodologies and ensuring seamless data exchange and integration with other European and international research environments within the EOSC framework.

The Blue-Cloud innovation potential is explored and unlocked by [dedicated demonstrators](#) as Virtual Labs (VLabs) co-designed with top-level marine researchers to demonstrate the power of the Blue-Cloud Open Science platform. The objective is to deploy a wide range of custom methods and technologies, such as softwares and algorithms, using cloud-based services in the Blue-Cloud VRE. The VLabs bring new data types, such as currents or carbon data, and are also able to incorporate the Data Discovery and Access (DD&AS) Service to their workflows.

This deliverable provides guidelines on how to use each of the VLabs developed during the Blue-Cloud 2026 project. Users are encouraged to discover and understand the services and run them

as proposed by the developers.

The document is structured by sections for each of the V Labs, from VLab one to five. Specifically, the handbook details five Virtual Labs covering coastal observation integration, currents, carbon-plankton dynamics, global fisheries, and a suite of marine environmental indicators (including heatwaves and storm severity). It provides developers and researchers with step-by-step workflows to explore, process, and download FAIR-compliant marine data, utilizing core platform features.

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1. Introduction

Welcome to the Users Handbook for the Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Laboratories (VLabs). This handbook serves as a comprehensive guide, providing essential information and practical instructions for effectively utilizing the VLabs.

The document is organized into five main sections, each dedicated to a specific VLab. These sections highlight the unique capabilities and objectives of each laboratory, ensuring users can navigate and apply their features efficiently. Notably, Section 6 (VLab 4) is further divided into four subsections, each focusing on a distinct marine environmental indicator, as detailed below:

- **VLab #1:** Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations Along Europe (ICOOE)
- **VLab #2:** Coastal Currents from Observation
- **VLab #3:** Carbon Plankton Dynamics
- **VLab #4:** Marine Environmental Indicators
 - Marine Heatwaves (MHW)
 - Ocean Heat Content
 - Eutrophication (TRIX)
 - Storm Severity Index Version 2 (SSI V2)
- **VLab #5:** Global Fisheries Atlas

Each section begins with an introduction to its respective VLab, outlining its purpose, scope, and **target users**. This is followed by a detailed explanation of the **state-of-the-art** methods employed and the **input data sources** used. A direct link to the VLab is also added in the **VLab availability** section.

To guide users in maximizing the potential of each VLab, a **step-by-step user guide** is included, offering clear and practical instructions. For those working with alternative data sources, dedicated subsections provide guidance on adapting the outlined procedures.

2. Registration to the Blue Cloud 2026 VRE

To be able to access Blue-Cloud 2026 services, users first need to register to the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform by creating an account on the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Gateway** (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Blue-Cloud Gateway

The registration process ends with a pop-up advertising “email verification” sent by the Blue Cloud management team. After the confirmation of registration, the user can start using the Blue Cloud platform. A video tutorial on how to register on Blue-Cloud is also available here: **[Blue-Cloud Hackathon - Using the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment](#)** .

Once logged in, a direct link to each VLab is provided.

BlueCloud2026 Thematic VLABs Virtual Laboratories conceived to support the developments of the Blue-Cloud2026 thematic VLABs.

Figure 2. How to access VLABs once logged in

The credentials allow access to the **Virtual Research Environment (VRE)** as well as four BlueCloud demonstrators and five Thematic VLABs (Figure 3). BlueCloud demonstrators were developed during the first BlueCloud project while VLABs are currently being developed during the Blue-Cloud 2026 project.

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Virtual labs

The Blue-Cloud thematic Virtual Labs (VLabs) are the main test beds for users to get the hang of the Blue-Cloud framework, exploiting the 10+ million datasets available via the Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS), as well as the easy access to the collaborative VLabs via D4Science.

The Blue-Cloud VLabs are real-life demonstrators for web-based open science and are open and available for testing by research communities. Each VLab comprises a series of applications for data processing, publishing of data results, and managing computation routines as well as services for collaboration, this way providing open science-friendly working environments for its users to analyse datasets and (re)generate research products

[Blue-Cloud2026 Virtual Labs & Data Lakes Booklet \(April 2024\)](#)

Carbon-Plankton Dynamics

This model will use carbon units to study nutrient availability, productivity, organic matter, and interactions in marine regions beyond MIRAMARE.

Global Fisheries Atlas

Explore the operational GRSF and FA VLabs in Blue-Cloud, enabling global access to fisheries data. Experience enhanced knowledge management and spatial data interoperability for impactful research and insights.

Coastal currents from observations

Improve integration and accuracy of ocean surface current data with Blue-Cloud 2026. Generate integrated maps using HF radar, drifter, and satellite altimetry data.

Figure 3. Virtual Labs web page

3. Introduction to VLab 1 “Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe”

This section is authored by João Vitorino, Vânia Lima (Instituto Hidrográfico), Juan Gabriel Fernández, Enrique Castrillo, Nikolaos Zarokanellos, Mélanie Juza, Miguel Charcos-Lloréns, Emma Reyes (SOCIB) and Jay Pearlman, Rene Garello (IEEE).

This VLab provides users with an environment that is specifically designed to support them in their explorations of the available coastal ocean information, developing and implementing tools to facilitate the access to different types of data, to data processing and quality control when needed, to exploitation of individual datasets and to integrated analysis of different types of data. It brings together observations collected by partners of the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories ([JERICO-RI](#)) with other available data from international data repositories.

VLab 1 supports the coastal ocean users through three Thematic Services:

- **Thematic Service 1**, addressing “**Transboundary processes and connectivity along the European margins**”, aims to support user interest in processes such as biological connectivity, contaminants spread, and impacts of river outflows along margins.
- **Thematic Service 2**, “**Extreme Events**”, focusing on coastal impacts of major storms.
- **Thematic Service 3**, “**Ocean glider**” shows the added value of repeated glider sections.

The VLab provides:

- Easy **identification** and access to available **observations** and complementary data for the coastal ocean areas of Europe;
- **Easy** handling/management of the available datasets, implementing, when required, the **pre-processing** (including additional quality control of the data) and **reformatting** of the data in a transparent way for the user and following the accepted Best Practices;
- Access to a panoply of exploitation tools aimed to **extract** from the datasets valuable information;
- Specific tools for the integrated **analysis** of different datasets, covering complementary aspects of the coastal ocean environment;
- **Visualization** tools adapted to each Thematic Service specific objectives.

One central idea in the base of the implementation of this VLab is the recognition of the multiplicity of skills that are required for a user to progress in the use of the available observations of the coastal ocean

environment to extract relevant information about the different processes that take place in these areas, of the impacts these processes promote. The simple identification of, and access to, the different available datasets is frequently not a guarantee that full extended use can be made of this data.

3.1. Target Users & Community

VLab 1 specifically aims to support the broad community of users that work on the coastal ocean environments of Europe. The Coastal Ocean Research community is clearly at the front of the high priority users of this VLab. The three thematic services proposed in this VLab bring to researchers the tools for processing, exploring, integrating and visualizing the different observations and associated complementary information that are available in coastal ocean areas, helping to remove the barriers to a comprehensive use of these datasets and boosting the understanding of the variety of processes operating in those areas. Users from the Blue Economy sectors or from Crisis Management entities can find in the Thematic Services offered by this VLab an easy way to access, explore and integrate the different observations or modelling results that can be relevant to support their operations. Environmental managers and policy makers can use the Virtual Lab as a rapid and powerful vehicle to build an integrated vision of geographical areas of interest and to explore different levels of understanding about the relevant processes and impacts occurring on these areas, in this easy improving the knowledge base that supports the decision making process. Finally, students, researchers and the general public can use Vlab 1 as a window to the coastal ocean, exploring available observations and complementary information using the different tools provided.

The VLab builds from the expertise in coastal ocean observation and research that is gathered in the JERICO-RI community, and a close interaction with this community is expected.

3.2. State of art

VLab 1 is based on methods that are commonly accepted by the scientific community and conform to the Best Practices recommendations and documents from OBPS and Aquadocs. In particular, the methods and tools implemented as part of VLab 1 follow the Best Practices developed by the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (JERICO) community for observations in coastal oceans using, for example, HF radars or fixed platforms, as well as Best Practices commonly adopted by the glider community.

Thematic Service #1 : Transboundary processes and connectivity along the European margins

Why we built these services

The Thematic Service #1 aims to provide a variety of tools that can support users in working with the observations and complementary information available for a given coastal ocean area, extracting information on transboundary transport and connectivity processes. Thematic Service #1 is structured on the basis of two central ideas about the coastal ocean environment:

- 1) The coastal oceans are areas of confluence of multiple influences and forcing mechanisms, many of which originate in domains that directly interact with the coastal ocean, such as the deep ocean, river and estuarine environments, and the atmosphere.
- 2) The coastal ocean environment contains specific mechanisms that promote the long distance propagation of perturbations. The bathymetric variations associated with shelf and slope topography, in combination with the presence of the coastal boundary, provide the basic mechanism allowing the coastal ocean to behave as a waveguide. Disturbances caused in a given location (due, for example, to wind forcing variability or to the impact of located continental or open ocean influences) can efficiently be transmitted along the continental margin in the form of barotropic shelf waves (Robinson, 1964) or, in the more general case of combined influence of bottom topography and stratification, as continental shelf waves (Allen, 1975; Brink, 1991). These processes allow that the disturbances can propagate sometimes by thousands of kilometers along the continental margin, impacting the coastal ocean conditions in areas far from the location of the disturbance. In the transition between the continental shelf and the open ocean, the large-scale density distribution (and associated geostrophic transport) interacts with the abrupt topographic change associated with the continental slope leading to the development of strong, slope intensified polewards flows through the JEBAR - Joint Effect of Baroclinicity and Relief - mechanism (Huthnance, 1984). These slope currents can transport open ocean influences (e.g. warm and high salinity waters or biological species) along the outer edges of the coastal ocean areas. They can also collect shelf and continental (e.g. river discharges) influence and propagate these influences to remote areas far from their origin.

In addition to these long distance along-margin propagation, important coastal ocean processes also act to promote across-margin propagation of disturbances. Particularly important examples of these processes are the development of large upwelling filaments extending one or two hundreds of kilometers offshore (areas exposed to upwelling favourable winds) and the important exchanges promoted by long submarine canyons. These processes all contribute to promote an important interaction between the coastal ocean and the complementary domains such as the open ocean environment or the continental domain.

Thematic Service #1 focus specifically on the processes described above, providing a broad range of tools that users can apply to extract from the available observations (and other complementary data) the relevant information about how these processes are expressed in the area of interest and how they are contributing to promote the interaction between the different parts of the coastal ocean domain inside this area. Since the processes described above operate mainly at subinertial time scales (periods longer than the local inertial periods), which are dominated by the effects of Earth rotation, the Thematic Service #1 analytical tools are restricted to low-pass filtered data.

Overview of the Thematic Service structure

The strategy implemented in Thematic Service #1 is based on the identification, access and analysis of data provided by different existing data aggregators. The thematic service can be viewed as structured in three main components (that correspond to three main services): data identification and access, data preprocessing and data analysis and visualization. Through the “data identification and access” component, a user interested in exploring aspects related to transboundary and connectivity processes can provide the details of the support request and the datasets that match this request can be identified and retrieved. The “data preprocessing component” provides a step required to adjust the datasets to the requirements of operation of the analysis tools and to the general purposes of the Thematic Service. Finally, the “data analysis and visualization” step allows the user to select a number of tools to analyze the selected data. Two main options for analysis and visualization are provided: the “Exploration Tools”, comprising tools for the analysis of the individual datasets, and the “Integration Tools”, comprising tools for the combined use of different datasets.

The pilot demonstrator of Thematic Service was implemented to operate for a specific regional domain - the Iberian coastal ocean area. The service is aimed to use the data collected by a number of monitoring infrastructures that are operated in this area by partners in Portugal and Spain and which, in many of the cases, integrate the JERICO Research Infrastructure. The way in which the Thematic Service was built, however, allows its future expansion – to a generic geographical domain and the inclusion of additional parameters of interest.

Thematic Service #1 was also implemented to allow the specification of 8 predefined variables of parameters of interest in coastal ocean research (surface and subsurface currents, temperature and salinity, waves and sea surface height, all these variables corresponding to physical Essential Ocean Variables EOVs). For the pilot demonstrator of this thematic the focus was given to one of these parameters - surface currents – which is particularly challenging for users given the different types of datasets that are provided by the data aggregators.

Identification and Access to Datasets

The Thematic Service #1 service starts with the user selection of the coastal ocean area and time period of interest. Based on these specifications, a number of datasets available for analysis are presented and can be selected by the user. The user-selected datasets are then downloaded from the correspondent data aggregators (provided accessibility is assured by the aggregator).

Preparing the Datasets for analysis

Before the selected data can be used in the analysis, it must follow a pre-processing stage aimed to bring each dataset to the proper format for development of the analysis and also to conform to the Thematic Service #1 specifications. This pre-processing step is transparent to the user: no outputs are generated, no inputs are required. It includes, for example, the identification of temporal gaps in the data, eventually filling short gaps by interpolation. It also includes the low pass filtering of data, when necessary, using a 36 hours running mean to retain only the subinertial variability.

Exploring Individual Datasets.

Two options for exploration of the individual datasets are provided under the “Exploration Tools” menu. The “Exploration Tools – Extraction and Visualization” option was designed to support the users in the process of manipulation of the datasets to extraction and visualization of the relevant information. The tool was implemented to allow, in next step development, the users to select the variables of interest from a set of 8 pre-defined variables (described above), some of which correspond to 2D fields while others correspond to 3D fields. At the present stage of development, the demonstrator is focused on the 2D surface current fields provided by HF radars observations or from numerical models results, which pose particularly challenging difficulties to non-expert users. Using this option, the user can extract to a file and visualize both the time series of (low-pass) surface current at specific (user selected) locations inside the specified user domain or the surface current fields at specific (user selected) times.

The “Exploration Tools - Basic Statistics” option allows the users to build a number of statistical analyses for the datasets and parameters of interest. The basic statistics product was developed using the standard statistical analysis applied to the marine research domain, which can be detailed in many references (e.g. Emery & Thomson, 1998). The “Basic Statistics” option was also implemented to be used for a selection of variables of interest, generating statistical outputs for each data set and variable selected by the users. These statistical outputs include Scalar Statistics, for all the variables selected, and, in addition, also Vectorial Statistics, for the current variables.

In the presently available demonstrator, restricted to the surface current fields provided by HF radar observations or numerical models, the “Basic Statistics” option produces two statistical analysis outputs, for each one of the datasets selected by the user. One of the outputs consists in the Scalar Statistics for the current components (U, eastward component and V, northward component) and for the current speed (C, magnitude of the velocity vector), calculated over the global time period selected by the user. The output of the Scalar Statistics product includes, for each geographical node (location of the HF radar low-pass filtered observations or location of the NEMO model horizontal grid) and for each one of the above indicated variables:

- The minimum (Umin, Vmin, Cmin), mean (Umean, Vmeam, Cmeam), and maximum (Umax, Vmax, Cmax) values;
- The variance (Uvar, Vvar, Cvar) and standard deviation (Ustd, Vstd, Cstd), measuring the variability of the data around the mean value for the period selected;
- The standard error of the mean (Usem, Vsem, Csem), indicating the precision of the mean estimate;
- The skewness (Uskew, Vskew, Cskew, corresponding to the third statistical moment, measuring the asymmetry of the probability distribution around its mean and revealing, for example, the direction of the extreme values) and the kurtosis (Ukurt, Vkury, Ckurt, corresponding to the fourth statistical moment, indicating how sharp the peak of the probability distribution is and revealing if data is clustered around the mean (higher kurtosis) or more distributed in the data interval, w lowe kurtosis);
- In addition, the total number of valid temporal records used to determine the basic scalar statistics in the node (NP) is also provided. This number is particularly important to interpret the statistics of HF radar observations, since problems with the operation of the system or low quality of the data (below quality control criteria) during some periods can affect either the overall coverage or specific spatial nodes, reducing the data registers that are available for the statistical analysis.

The scalar statistics output can be exported as a table. The visualization of results for this option was, for the present demonstrator, restricted to the visualization of the fields of mean, maximum and minimum surface current speed.

The second output produced by the “Basic Statistics” option corresponds to the Vectorial Statistics for the low frequency (subinertial) surface current field, calculated over the selected time period. For each location corresponding to the spatial nodes, these statistics include:

- the mean vectorial speed (VMean, in m/s);
- the direction of the mean vector (MVDir, in degrees, counted clockwise relative to geographic North);
- the mean vector variance (MVVar, in m^2/s^2) and the mean vector standard deviation (MVStD, in m/s);
- the mean vector standard error (MVStErr, in m/s);
- the principal direction (PDir, in degrees counted clockwise relative to geographical North), the direction along which current fluctuations relative to the mean are higher;
- the (Neuman) stability factor (StabFct, in %);
- the lengths of the major and minor axis (MajAxis, MinAxis, in m/s), which correspond to the axis of, respectively, maximum and minimum current fluctuations in regard to the vectorial mean;
- the number of valid time steps used to calculate statistics (NP).

The vectorial statistics output can be exported as a table. In the current version of the thematic service 1, the visualization of the vectorial statistics is restricted to the graphics of the mean velocity vectors and to the current variability ellipses, both overimposed on the bathymetry of the area selected by the user.

The basic statistics products described above can then allow the user to better characterize the low-frequency (subinertial) surface currents in a given geographical region and for a given time period of interest, based on the available observations collected by HF radar systems or from results of the NEMO model made available at the Copernicus Marine System.

Integrating Datasets

A second set of tools that the users can choose to analyze the datasets that were selected is available from the “Integration Tools” menu. Here a set of tools is provided to support the user in the combined analysis of different datasets, building add-value products of interest. As an example of this type of tools, the demonstrator that is presently available to users offers the “Integration Tools - Pathways Trajectories” option. This option allows the user to combine surface currents observed by HF radar systems with surface currents obtained from a numerical model, in an evaluation of the advection of a single surface particle that was deployed at a geographical position and initial time both selected by the user. The Pathways Trajectories tool can be relevant to users interested in exploring the pathways followed, for example, by a surface object or a passive tracer under the action of the low-frequency (subinertial) dynamics that affected the coastal ocean domain specified by the user. Frequently, these studies made use of the surface current fields provided by numerical models. The availability of HF radar observations, covering parts of

the European coastal ocean areas, brings the possibility of combining these two sources of information about the surface current field to produce refined estimates for the surface transport.

The “Pathways Trajectories” tool requires that surface current fields from the NEMO model are available for the coastal ocean domain and time period of interest. From these, the advection of the single surface particle is calculated based only on the NEMO daily mean surface currents. In addition, if HF radar data is available, covering different subdomains of the total domain selected by the users, then this data is used to generate a second estimate of the trajectory followed by the particle trajectory. The calculus of this second trajectory uses the hourly low-pass (subinertial) surface currents observed by HF radar, in the geographical areas covered by these systems, and integrates the daily mean surface currents provided NEMO model, which are used to advect the particle in the geographical areas that are not covered by HF radars or (if inside an area of HF radar coverage) during the periods of gaps in the HF radar observation.

In the present demonstrator, a number of simplified approaches were used in order to reduce the computational cost and time required to generate the products answering the user request. The trajectories are computed from a simple advective scheme, in which the new position of the particle is calculated from the present position and from the velocity defined at the midpoint (in time) between the two positions. And, in the calculation of the trajectories, the transport of the surface particle is based on the surface current data that is closer to the particle and not on the interpolation of surface current nodes for the position of the particle. Following this first phase of opening the “Pathways Trajectories” analysis tool to the user community, after the assessment of the performance of the tool, these simplified approaches can be progressively improved.

The results generated by the “Integration Tools - Pathways Trajectories” option can be exported as a table providing the locations in time for the two trajectories. The results are visualized in a graph that combines the two trajectories, one based only on the NEMO model surface currents, the second one based on the combination of HF radar currents and NEMO model currents, which are presented over the topography of the area. The user can then easily identify how the coastline configuration and topographic features can impact the transport pathways in the coastal ocean domain. It can also easily assess how, for each specific problem, HF radar observations can improve the calculus of the trajectories for surface drift from those based only on the numerical models.

Thematic Service #2: Extreme events

Why we built these services

The Thematic Service #2 provides users with access to a portfolio of tools aimed to support the research on and understanding of the impacts of extreme events on the coastal ocean regions of Europe. The designation of “extreme event” comprises a broad range of phenomena that are rare, highly energetic, and often short-lived, and that show a significant deviation from the normal (statistical) conditions. They comprise, among others, extreme storms (e.g. hurricanes) promoting energetic waves and important storm surge phenomena, marine heat waves, extreme salinity events, ocean acidification episodes or coastal flooding.

Sustained observation of the evolution of coastal ocean conditions along the European margin is presently achieved by a variety of monitoring infrastructures. The integrated analysis of this broad range of data can unveil key aspects of the extreme events, in particular can show in detail the nature of their impact on the coastal ocean environment and on human activities. Thematic Service #2 was implemented to explore these capacities and provide support to the users interested in progressing in the understanding of these processes.

Overview of Thematic Service Structure

Similarly to the strategy developed for Thematic Service #1, the pilot demonstrator for Thematic Service #2 was also implemented for the specific regional domain of the overall Iberian coastal ocean region. Like Thematic Service #1, the Thematic Service #2 demonstrator was structured in such a way that it will easily allow its future application to other regional coastal ocean domains.

The pilot demonstrator for Thematic Service #2 was restricted to the analysis of the impacts of the energetic waves and currents that are associated with the passage of extreme storms. These conditions can considerably affect the coastal ocean areas and coasts of Europe, leading to considerable environmental, economic and human impacts. Unlike Thematic Service #1, in which the users can search the datasets that are available from aggregators to identify the relevant data that can be used, the demonstrator for Thematic Service #2 was built following a different strategy. Here, users can explore pre-defined extreme storm periods, for which the associated datasets were previously prepared inside VLab 1. The thematic service proposes to users to explore the following 3 extreme storm events. These include:

- the Ophelia Storm/Hurricane, one of the major hurricanes of the 2017 Atlantic hurricane season, that formed on the 9 October 2017, intensified as a major hurricane on the 14 October 2017 south of the Azores and progressed northeastward towards Ireland and Great Britain, becoming dissipating on the 18 October 2017. Following the analysis of the wave conditions affecting the global Iberian Margin domain during the period of passage of this storm, the period considered for analysis was restricted to extend from the 14 October 2017 to the 17 October 2017. This is the period covered in the different datasets prepared for evaluation of the impacts of this storm on the coastal ocean off the Iberian Margin;
- the Emma storm, a powerful late-winter storm that affected the western European margin in late February early March 2018, leading to heavy rain, snow and locally damaging winds to parts of the Iberian Peninsula, Spain, Great Britain and Ireland. Emma associated extreme waves were to impact considerable the benthic marine organisms along the coast of southwest Spain (Garcia-de-Lomas et al., 2019), providing a particularly interesting example to explore the impacts on the seafloor conditions. In Thematic Service #2, the period of data used to characterize the impacts of storm Emma on the global Iberian Margin domain was considered to extend from 25 February 2018 to 7 March 2018.
- the Hurricane Leslie, initially formed on 23 September 2018 south-southwest of the Azores, but that from 11 October 2018, when it passed offshore Madeira Archipelago, rapidly migrated northeastward, directly impacting the central part of the western Portuguese coast on the night of the 13 October 2018, entering on the mainland and rapidly dissipating on the 14 October 2018. The extreme waves associated with the passage of this storm were concentrated in a short time window and mostly affecting the western Portuguese and Spanish margins, thus providing a good example of the influence of this type of energetic and spatially concentrated events that can directly hit the continental areas. In thematic Service #2, the period of data considered to better characterise the impacts of Hurricane Leslie on the coastal ocean environment around Iberian Margin extends from 13 to 14 October 2018.

Two options were defined in the Thematic Service #2 for the analysis of the datasets available for each storm period. The “Exploration Tools” comprises the tools to be used for the analysis of the individual data sets and is not already available in the demonstrator that is open to the users. The “Integration Tools” comprises a number of tools to be used in the combined analysis of different datasets. The demonstrator that is presently available explores the “Integration Tools” concept and offers two options, the “Integration Tools - Impacts on the Bottom” option and “Integration Tools - Impacts on Offshore Structures” option. These are described in detail below.

Identification and Access to Datasets

As mentioned above, the Thematic Service #2 uses previously prepared sets of data that are used in the preparation of the different products required by the user for the analysis of the storm that was selected. The currently implemented demonstrator for this thematic service combines observations of the bottom characteristics of the coastal ocean area of interest with numerical modelling results on the dynamical processes affecting the area. The option to restrict the characterisation of the dynamical processes based only on numerical model results was dictated by the interest in showing, at this early stage of the use of the service, the impacts of extreme storm on the seafloor, for coastal ocean domain of an important dimension. The numerical modelling products used here readily allow the characterisation of these bottom impacts in the global area (Iberian Margin). The use of observations of the conditions, such as measurements from multiparametric buoys, is planned for a next step development, but these datasets are more restricted in terms of spatial coverage.

The characteristics of the seabed substrate for the global area was built from the EMODnet Geology project, which collects and harmonizes marine geological data from the European seas. Data collected by the different national geological surveys, using the national standards and classifications, is harmonized in EMODnet Geology using the Folk's sediment triangle (based on the percentages of mud, sand and gravel present in the sediments) with a hierarchy of 16, 7 and 5 substrate classes (Guinan et al., 2020). The Thematic Service#2 pilot demonstrator uses the [Folk7 product](#). In Thematic Service #2, the Folk7 data provided by EMODNET Geology was organized in files corresponding to a total of 14 regional areas comprising the global domain of application of the thematic service. The global seabed substrate, based on the EMODnet Geology Folk7 product used in Thematic Service #3, is shown in the figure below.

The bathymetry and seabed substrate characteristics of the global Iberian Margin domain are used by the thematic service for the analysis of all the storm events considered. The bathymetry of the global area was built based on the EMODnet Digital Bathymetry (DTM) 2024 (tiles E3, F3, E4, F4), with a resolution of 1/16 arc minute of longitude x 1/16 arc minute of latitude (circa 115m x 115m). To ease the handling of this bathymetric data in the analysis tools, the DTM2024 data was organized in the 14 regional areas indicated above, at the positions where seabed substrate data was defined.

Figure 4. Global seabed substrate based on Folk7 classification used in Thematic Service 2, with details for specific subareas.

The characterisation of the environmental conditions associated with each storm period is based on two sets of numerical model results provided by the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS). The characterization of the wave conditions affecting the global area covered by the demonstrator during the period defined for each storm, is based on the wave parameters obtained from the CMEMS Atlantic -Iberian Biscay Irish-Ocean Wave Reanalysis product (IBI_MULTIYEAR_WAV_005_006) generated from the MFWAM model (Gómez et al., 2025) developed by Météo France, with a 1/36° resolution in longitude and latitude (about 3 km resolution in latitude and longitude). This system assimilates significant wave height altimeter data and wave spectral data (Envisat and CFOSAT), supplied by Météo France and is fed by ECMWF (ERA5

reanalysis) hourly winds. The product offers hourly instantaneous fields of different wave parameters and related variables. For the Thematic Service #2 the variables extracted from these files comprise:

- the significant wave height (hm_0 , in m)
- the wave mean period from variance spectral density second frequency moment (tm_{02} , in s)
- the wave mean period from variance spectral density inverse frequency (tm_{10} , in s)
- the mean wave direction (m_{dir} , in degrees)
- the wave peak period (T_p , in s)
- the wave direction at spectral peak (dir_{tp} , in degrees)
- The maximum wave height (hc_{max} , in m)

These wave parameters were defined for each one of the 14 geographical areas and at the positions where seabed substrate Folk7 data is defined.

The characterization of the current conditions that prevailed in the same geographical area, during the same time periods, is based on the hourly fields of barotropic current generated from the numerical simulations of the NEMO model, which are available in the CMEMS IBI_MULTIYEAR_PHY_005_002 product (Castrillo-Acuña et al., 2025). The model has a spatial resolution of 1/36 degrees (about 2-3 km) in the horizontal and 50 constant depth vertical levels. The available datasets for this hourly re-analysis product comprises the surface current and barotropic current. No information about the current in the water column is provided in this product. Consequently, in the presently available demonstrator for Thematic Service #2, the barotropic current is used to characterize the current conditions that affect the water column and the seafloor, instead of using the total (barotropic plus baroclinic) current. This option can be justified since the highly energetic periods considered in Thematic Service #2 occur, most typically, during late fall or winter periods. In those periods the water column over the continental shelf is poorly stratified due to the vertical mixing promoted by energetic waves and by the loss of heat to the atmosphere. The highly energetic periods associated with extreme storms lead to additional strong vertical mixing of the shelf waters. In those conditions, the shelf currents promoted by winds or tides, are found to be rather barotropic. For each storm period, the NEMO model barotropic current data is organized in the 14 geographical areas described before and projected at the locations of the Folk7 substrate data.

When using Thematic Service #2, the user selects the geographical area of interest and the extreme storm of interest. As referred previously, in order to allow a faster processing and optimized performance, all the datasets were projected in the 14 geographical areas presently described, at the position of the Folk7 seabed substrate data. In the present phase of development of the Thematic Service #2 demonstrator, it

is suggested that users restrict, if possible, their domains of interest to 2 or 3 of the 14 geographical areas. This would help evaluate the system's performance, leading to improvements that could reduce computational costs and allow the definition of gradually larger geographical domains of interest.

Impacts of extreme storms on the coastal ocean seafloor

The “Integration Tools - Impacts on the Bottom” is aimed to allow the users to assess how storm conditions impact the coastal ocean seafloor. Evaluating these bottom impacts is particularly important to understand aspects such as bottom sediment erosion, impacts on bottom habitats impacts, impacts on bottom structures (e.g anchors for fixed platforms), remobilization of contaminants fixed on bottom sediments, among many other aspects.

While extreme storm events have a short duration, the impacts they originate in coastal ocean conditions can affect the long term evolution and the global cycles. Examples of this are the massive damages that major storms can induce on the benthic ecosystem (e.g. Garcia-de-Lomas et al., 2019). Or the potential reduction of the impacts of vertical mixing and re-aeration of the water column associated with the oxidation of continental shelf sediments that are resuspended by storms events, with potential impacts on the global cycles of marine dissolved oxygen and carbon (Bianucci et al, 2018). Impacts on the bottom are also, of course, particularly important for many economical and research activities that are held in coastal ocean areas.

A large body of literature exists for the topics of waves and currents impacts on the bottom sedimentary cover. The existing research includes field observations, laboratory experiments, theoretical formulation and numerical modelling approaches. Much of the present knowledge about how these processes operate and how we can operationally address them, is based on empirical formulation that was developed from the approaches mentioned before. The analysis products implemented in the “Impacts on the Bottom” option closely follow a body of work presented by van Rijn (2007a, 2007b, 1984a, 1984b, 1984c).

The starting point for the analysis of the impacts on bottom sedimentary cover, for the user selected geographical domain of interest and storm period, is the characterization of the bottom characteristics. The pre-prepared files containing the EMODnet Geology seabedSubstrate Folk7 classification, for each one of the 14 geographical areas, provide the basic characterization of the bottom substrate using the following 7 classes:

- Mud
- Sandy Mud

- Muddy Sand
- Sand
- Coarse Substrat
- Mixed Sediments
- Rocks & Boulders

For each one of these classes we associated other characteristics of the seabed substrate by integrating other sources of information. The Wentworth (1922) classification is used to define the grain size characteristics associated with each class and to define the mean grain size (D_{50}) of the bottom sediments. The classification presented by van Rijn (2007a, Table 1) for bed samples consisting of mixtures of clay, silt and sand is used to associate to the Folk7 classes that match these classes a number of properties such as the cohesive character of the sediments and the percentages of sand, silt, clay plus fine silt and biogenic material. In the present demonstrator of Thematic Service #2, these properties are associated with each Folk 7 class for the overall Iberian Margin geographical domain, where the thematic service is defined. However, in future phases of development, these properties can easily be refined, in order to match more detailed characterisations of the bottom sediments that may become available in specific subdomains of the area.

The second step in the analysis of bottom impacts associated with extreme storms is to characterise the near bottom dynamics associated with waves and currents. In the “Impacts on the Bottom” tool this requires reading the pre-prepared files that contain the EMODnet DTM2024 bathymetry, WFWAM wave parameters and the NEMO barotropic currents, which are (as explained above) defined at the seabed substrate data locations. The WFWAM wave parameters (in the user selected area and for the time period defined for the selected storm) are used to define the two groups of results that are delivered from this tool.

First, the maximum significant wave height at each location of seabed substrate data is identified in the time series of wave parameters. This corresponds to higher waves that affected that location during the period of influence of the storm. From the NEMO model results we extract, at each location of the seabed substrate Folk7 data, the barotropic current for the time of maximum significant wave height. Based on the linear theory of surface gravity waves and using the associated WFWAM wave parameters at the time of maximum wave height, the NEMO barotropic current (which corresponds also to the near bottom current) and the EMODnet DTM2024 bottom, we calculate the wave length of these waves (solving the dispersion relation) and the corresponding wavelength in the presence of the current, the wave orbital velocity at the bottom and the amplitude of the orbital motion at the bottom.

These results are included in a first output (that the user can export as a file) with the characterisation of the forcing conditions over the bottom sedimentary cover that are associated with the extreme waves that the storm promoted in each location inside the geographical domain of interest. This output includes the geographic position (in longitude and latitude) of each location where Folk 7 seabed substrate is defined, the time that corresponds to the maximum values of significant wave height at that location, the significant wave height (HS), the peak period (TP), the wave direction at peak period (DIRTP), the wavelength (WVL) and the corresponding wavelength modified by the current (WVLC), the orbital velocity at the bottom (UorbB), the amplitude of orbital motion at the bottom (AOrb), the maximum wave height (HMAX), the eastward (UBT) and northward (VBT) of the barotropic current, the barotropic current speed (CURR) and direction (CDIR).

From these results, the impacts of waves and (barotropic) currents on the bottom can be calculated for both the times of most energetic waves associated with the storm (first group of outputs) and the less energetic conditions found during the time period defined for the storm (second group of outputs). In the “Impacts on the Bottom” service these steps involved:

- The determination of the dimensionless particle size;
- The calculation of the critical Shields number for non-cohesive sediments for different ranges of dimensionless particle size;
- The calculation of the critical shear stress at seabed for non-cohesive sediments and of the generic critical shear stress at the seabed, taking in account the cohesive or non-cohesive characteristics of the bottom sediments associated with the seabed substrate characteristics. This involves, for cohesive particles, estimating also the particle-particle interaction effects such as clay coating effects and packing effects;
- The estimation of the current related bed roughness, taking in account the different bedforms, of the grain skin friction coefficient and current related friction coefficient and of the instantaneous grain related bed shear stress associated with currents;
- The estimation of the shear stress at the bottom promoted by wave, including the calculus of the wave related bedform roughness and of the wave related friction coefficient leading to the estimation of the instantaneous grain related bed shear stress due to waves;
- The estimation of the effective shear bed shear stresses relate with waves and with currents (estimating the wave-current interaction factor);
- Integration of the results above in the estimation of the combined shear stress at bottom promoted by the combined effects of currents and waves

- Calculation of the characteristics of the bedforms promoted by the waves and the currents; at the present stage of development only the characteristics of bedforms promoted by waves are delivered, in the form of ripples wavelength (WRL) and ripples height (WRH)
- Estimation of the bedload transport in critical criteria are verified (QB)
- Estimation of the suspended transport of sediments (QS) promoted by the mean current and including the wave stirring in the sedimentary cover, involving the determination of the dimensionless bed shear parameter, of the reference volume concentration near bed, of the size of particles in suspension, of the sediment fall velocity (first for single suspended particles in clear water as a first guess, then calculating the non-dimensional reference concentration profile from Rouse profile based on the first guess and finally calculating the corrections factors for determination of final formulation of the particle fall velocity), of the suspension number (ZSUSPN) based on the concentration reference at 1m above bottom and the final adimensional reference concentration profile (CONC(iz)) calculated at a total of iz=4 predefined heights above the seabed (Z(iz)) from from the Rouse profile and based on the final fall velocity. The 4 pre-defined depths correspond to 1m above the bottom, 5 m above the bottom, the middle of the water column and 9/10 of the total water column.
- Estimation of the total transport of sediments (Qtot = QB+QS).

Three outputs are generated from this step of estimation the impacts on the bottom sedimentary cover shear by the actions of waves and currents during the maximum wave height conditions associated with the storm. The first output includes, for each location where the Folk7 seabed substrate is defined and for the time at which the maximum significant wave height occurred at that location, the following variables (see the description in the paragraphs above): TCRO (in N/m^2), CURR (in m/s), TAUCgrain (in N/m^2), TAUC (in N/m^2), TAUCeff (in N/m^2), UorbB (in m/s), TAUWgrain (in N/m^2), TAUW (in N/m^2), TAUWeff (in N/m^2), UCW (in m/s), TAUCWgrain (in N/m^2), TAUCW (in N/m^2), TRATIO1, TAUCWeff (in N/m^2) and TRATIO2. The second output reports (also for each location and corresponding time) the characteristics of the bedforms associated with currents (CRippL, CRippH, both in m - not presently available and indicate with a zero value) and with waves (WRippL, WRippH, both in m). The third output includes (again, at each location and for the corresponding time) the estimates for the sediment transport and distribution in the water column: QB (in kg/s/m), QSC (in kg/s/m), QTOTAL (in kg/s/m), ZSUSPN , followed by the 4 pairs Z(iz) and CONC(iz).

In order to contrast the extreme wave impacts on the area with the impacts associated with the low energy conditions, an approach similar to the one described above was also developed for the lowest wave conditions (minimum of the significant wave height) that occurred for the time period of the storm,

at each location where Folk7 seabed substrate is defined. This approach leads to the generation of three outputs, similar to the ones described above.

Impacts on offshore structures

The “Integration Tools - Impacts on the Offshore Structures” option was implemented to provide additional information about the impacts of extreme storms on the coastal ocean environment, focussing the impacts on the water column. Although consisting in a simplified analysis, this tool can be used to provide a first assessment of the impacts of each predefined storm on structures located offshore, such as aquaculture installations or offshore wind mills. The geographical area of interest defined by the user is discretized in 9 locations (center of the domain, vertices and midpoint of each side). For the locations that are located offshore the coast, a total 5 vertical levels ($Z(ip)$, with $ip=1$ to 4) uniformly distributed between the surface and the bottom are defined. For each of these points we calculate, for the times corresponding to the maximum wave, the wavelength and wave orbital velocity from the WFWAM data. The output generated includes the coordinates (longitude, latitude) of the location at which Fork7 seabed substrate are defined, the time corresponding the maximum significant wave height, the significant wave height (HS , in m), the wave peak period (TP , in s), the wave peak direction ($DIRTP$, in degrees counted clockwise from the geographical North), the wavelength (WVL , in m), the wavelength modified by the presence of the current ($WVLC$, in m), the maximum wave height ($HMAX$, in m), the 5 pairs of depth ($Z(ip)$, in m) and wave orbital velocity ($UHsZ1(ip)$), the barotropic current speed ($CURR$, in m/s) and direction ($CDIR$, in degrees, counted anticlockwise from East). The visualization of these outputs presents the vertical profiles of wave orbital velocity and barotropic current, from surface to bottom, for the points located at the corners of the geographical domain chosen by the user and offshore the coast (maximum of 4 profiles if all points located in the marine domain).

A similar procedure is also developed for the conditions associated with the minimum values of significant wave height, at each location, leading to a similar output but for the (contrasting) less energetic wave conditions found in the time interval defined for each storm.

Thematic Service #3 : Ocean Glider

Thematic Service #3 (TS#3) is a toolbox for the computation and visualization of physical variables from gliders as well as derived variables that are relevant for both science and society.

The Ibiza Channel (IC), a well-known biodiversity hotspot and a choke point of the western Mediterranean Sea with complex topography and circulation, is used here as an example. Significant water mass variability takes place in the IC throughout time and space that impacts the marine ecosystem (e.g., Bluefin Tuna, Jellyfish). This water mass variability is driven by the interaction between basin-scale circulation, mesoscale dynamics, and seasonal forcing. Since 2011, we have been monitoring the IC quasi-continuously using ocean gliders to understand the ocean processes that occurred. The repeated high-resolution glider sections allow us to describe and understand the ocean variability from daily/weekly to interannual scales. Repeatable glider sections have been increased across coastal boundary systems, forming a key component of the Boundary Ocean Observing Network by providing sustained, high-resolution observations that capture the strong spatial gradients and temporal variability characteristic of coastal-to-open-sea exchanges.

Tools such as this Thematic Service #3 will facilitate our understanding of the physical variability of the system and the impact of climatic change by examining key EOv and derived parameters such as temperature (T), salinity (S), density (ρ), and geostrophic velocity (GV). Thematic service #3 allowed the user to produce vertical sections of temperature (T), salinity (S), density (ρ), and geostrophic velocity (GV).

TS#3 can be seen as a virtual laboratory built around a two-step workflow. In the first step, it enables users to process Slocum raw binary data and generate standardized datasets. In the second step, these datasets can be post-processed to create advanced, gridded data products and visual plots—all accessible through a user-friendly web interface.

In summary, this virtual lab allows users to extract and analyze key ocean EOv and derived parameters to better understand the regional ocean circulation and its impact on marine ecosystems.

Currently, it's important to highlight that only raw data from Slocum gliders can be processed in the first step. However, users can skip this step if they already have glider data in OG1.0 netCDF format—a community standard developed by the OceanGliders global initiative.

TS#3 provides three main components:

- Two Python toolboxes.
- A web-based viewer.

The two toolboxes are meant to be used within Jupyter Notebooks:

- The first one, `glider_converter`, is a Python package designed to convert Slocum raw binary data and metadata into an OG1.0-compliant netCDF file.

- The second one, `glider_postproc`, processes that netCDF file to generate a gridded advanced data product. This includes interpolated vertical sections of potential temperature, salinity, density, and geostrophic velocity, presented on a regular grid that follows the glider's path.

The output is a well-documented netCDF file that adheres to FAIR data principles and community standards.

The viewer allows users to explore these results in an intuitive and interactive way.

Among the three components, the core element is the `glider_postproc` toolbox. It provides flexibility to customize the output—for instance, selecting specific sections of a mission for gridding or applying quality control filters to ensure data reliability.

As a whole, Thematic Service 3 opens up new possibilities to process repeated glider sections—also known as endurance lines—from virtually any ocean region, leveraging the new OG1.0 data format. It also allows for the FAIR publication of the resulting advanced data products.

Typical Use Case

As an example, after logging into the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and navigating to the ICOOE Virtual Lab, 2 choices are available:

- Upload a compressed folder containing Slocum raw binary data to your workspace,
- Or provide the URL of an existing standard netCDF file in OG1.0 format. Please note that the toolbox allows formats other than OG1.0 as long as they are similar.

If the user begins with raw data, the first step will be to use the `glider_converter` toolbox. This tool transforms the raw mission output and accompanying metadata into a standardized OG1.0 netCDF file, ready for further processing.

Next comes the post-processing stage using the `glider_postproc` toolbox. Before launching it, it's important to plan the workflow carefully. The user will start by reviewing the glider's mission trajectory and identifying the section(s) of interest—the specific path or paths to be analyzed.

We recommend plotting the glider's full track on a map so you can visually select the start and end points that define the section to be processed. The toolbox will then extract and include all data along this defined section to generate the advanced data product.

Once this step is complete, the user can:

- View the results through the web-based viewer provided by TS#3,
- Or download and explore the gridded netCDF product directly for a deeper analysis.

Users are encouraged to iterate and refine their results—adjust the section boundaries, tweak processing parameters, or even combine outputs from multiple glider missions by repeating the process. This flexibility enables tailoring analysis to specific regions, events, or scientific questions.

By following these steps, users will gain a comprehensive understanding of glider-derived observations and unlock valuable insights into coastal ocean dynamics.

3.3. Input data sources

At the present stage of development of VLab 1, users can access and work with the following variables/datasets:

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
Surface Currents	Coastal high frequency (HF) radars retrieved from the European HFR node THREDDS catalog (data version 3.0)	https://thredds.hfrnode.eu:8443/thredds/catalog.html
Surface Currents	NEMO Model, daily mean surface current fields retrieved from CMEMS	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/IBI_MULTIYEAR_PHY_005_002/description and https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/IBI_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_005_001/services
Bottom topography	Topography used for plotting (10 m coastline) and bathymetry	https://www.natureearthdata.com/

Table 1a. VLab 1 Thematic Service #1 Input data sources.

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
-----------	--------------	-------------

Wave Parameters	High-resolution wave reanalysis multi-year product for the Iberia-Biscay-Ireland (IBI) area based on the WFWAM model, hourly fields of wave parameter retrieved from CMEMS	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/IBI_MULTIYEAR_WAV_005_006/description
Barotropic Current	NEMO model, hourly fields of barotropic current retrieved from CMEMS	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/IBI_MULTIYEAR_PHY_005_002/description
Bottom Sedimentary Cover	Folk7 characterisation of seabed substrate from EMODNET	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Bottom topography	EMODnet Digital Bathymetry (DTM 2024). High resolution topography produced by the EMODnet Bathymetry Consortium	https://doi.org/10.12770/cf51df64-56f9-4a99-b1aa-36b8d7b743a1
Bottom topography	Topography used for plotting (10 m coastline) and bathymetry	https://www.naturalearthdata.com/

Table 1b. VLab 1 Thematic Service #2 Input data sources.

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
Sea water pressure	OG1.0 (or equivalent) format netCDF file representing a glider	Data can be downloaded from any data server or repository specialised in glider datasets.
Sea water temperature		

<p>Sea water practical salinity</p>	<p>mission performing several transects along a single path.</p>	<p>Data shall be transformed into the accepted formats before further processing using Thematic Service #3 tools. Example data repository: https://apps.socib.es/data-catalog/?platform_type=Glider</p>
--	--	--

Table 1c. VLab 1 Thematic Service #3 Input data sources.

3.4. VLab availability

This VLab is available through the Blue-Cloud gateway at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/icooe>.

3.5. Step by step guideline to use the VLab

Users access the VLab from their own account in the Blue Cloud gateway (mandatory). Accessing the [ICOOE VLab](#), the user can find 3 thematic services (TS) available, Thematic Service #1 (Transboundary Processes and Connectivity), Thematic Service #2 (Extreme events) and Thematic Service #3 (Ocean Glider).

This step by step guide describes how to use the VLab for the following activities:

- How to identify, analyze and integrate coastal data along the European margin (cf. Sec. 3.5.1);
- How to identify extreme events impacts on coastal ocean areas of Europe (cf. Sec. 3.5.2);
- How to process glider data (cf. Sec. 3.5.3).

3.5.1. How to identify, analyze and integrate coastal data along the European margin

Thematic Service 1 launches a dashboard (Figure 5), showing a map of the European coastal ocean domain on the right side, and several user options on the left side.

Figure 5. Dashboard for Thematic Service 1.

Using the mouse/keyboard on the map, users can move around in the domain and zoom in/zoom out the geographical area (Figure 6). The geographical area of interest can be drawn directly on the map or can be input in the appropriate fields in the Coordinates box (*min* stands for minimum latitude/longitude coordinate, *max* stands for maximum latitude/longitude coordinate). To draw the area of interest directly in the map, click the *Draw* button from the Coordinates box and then draw the area of interest using the mouse. Clicking the garbage bin symbol (next to Draw) resets the geographical selection made with the *Draw* button. The information about the coordinates of the selected box is saved and presented in the Coordinates box on the left of the dashboard. The user can then proceed by selecting the time interval of interest, in the Time range box on the left side, to indicate, in a calendar, the year, month, day of the start and end of the time period of interest. For response efficiency reasons, at the moment, the data request is limited to 7 days. In future developments the efficiency issues will be worked, in order to extend the time period of analysis. This will happen over the next two years (2026 to 2028).

In the drop-down menu the user can select the physical parameters available, comprising surface currents, surface temperature, surface salinity, subsurface currents, subsurface temperature, subsurface salinity and sea surface height. At the present stage of development of this Thematic Service, the demonstrator only allows the selection of surface currents, which are retrieved for 2 sub-systems, concerning surface currents from high frequency radar (HFR) data and surface currents from the NEMO

model. High frequency radar data is retrieved from the European HFR node for all the available networks and the NEMO model data is retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service.

Figure 6. Example of the selection of an area of interest, by the user.

After the user selection is finished, a check on the Overlap Area (OA) and Overlap Time (OT) is done, to make the user aware of the data availability from the selection made before. This way a new selection can be easily performed, if that is the case. The Available Data button becomes highlighted when all the mandatory selection fields are completed and the information of the available data is displayed afterwards, after clicking the Available data button (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Available data button and downloading data from aggregators.

Access to the data and download to the Dashboard VRE is done in a transparent way regarding the user and involves a process of connection to the data providers, with authentication in the case of the CMEMS data access. The data download for the European HFR node thredds catalog is done using the [NetCDF Subset Service](#) available and netCDF 4.1.3 data formats are downloaded. The Nemo Model surface currents retrieved from CMEMS are accessed through the Copernicus Marine Toolbox (version 1.3.4) API in a Python integrated development environment. By using the Python Library (API) and the Subset function, it is possible to download a subset of the datasets of interest (by specifying the variables, geographical area, time range, and depth), as only specific parts of the data are required.

It should be noted that the data download feature is dependent on the successful connections established with the mentioned providers, which includes the login feature. Therefore, we emphasise the need to, at times, retry the data download dashboard feature, as the primary connections can sporadically fail at times due to the thredds server being down, authentication failures, and/or other updates related problems. The periodic updates of the Copernicus Marine Toolbox also require the verification of the correct workflow of the data download functionality.

The European HFR node data download always includes a broader time range than requested by the user, to accommodate data pre-processing requirements. To allow a more manageable handling of datasets comprising a long time period, the system segments the data to be downloaded in blocks of limited time length. When the data downloads start, a progress spinner appears right next to the Choose this Data

button. When the data downloads are completed, the user is informed of the final status of the data download (including details about the data and datasets downloaded) via a message that appears in the dashboard, right next to the Choose this Data button (Figure 8). There is a Show Logs menu, in which the user can access a session report on the tasks performed, including the ones involving the data download.

Figure 8. Status of data download and data pre-processing progress check.

Following the downloading of the relevant datasets to be used, the Dashboard VRE proceeds with the pre-processing of these datasets. This stage, also transparent to the user, involves a number of steps that aim to transform the data in such a way that it becomes consistent with the specific requirements of the Thematic Service #1. For the HF radar data download from the European node, these steps involve the definition of a common regular grid comprising all the observed nodes, the introduction of an additional quality control criteria based on the data quality parameters provided, the identification of time gaps in the data for each node and the time interpolation of the small time gaps, the low-pass filtering of the hourly data using a running mean of 36 hours. For NEMO surface current fields, the pre-processing stage includes the detection of eventual time gaps and, in case the time period selected by the user extends from times covered by the low resolution grid product IBI_MULTIYEAR_PHY_005_002 to periods covered

by the high resolution grid product IBI_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_005_001, it interpolates the low resolution data in the high resolution grid. This procedure aims to ensure the compatibility of data retrieved from each one of the two products in the following exploitation/integration steps. NEMO fields correspond to daily means so no low-pass filtering is required.

After the preprocessing step is completed, the user is sent to a window presenting the different analysis that is possible to develop with the data sets selected, which is the Advanced Analysis Options menu. The Advanced Analysis Options menu includes Exploration Tools aimed to explore each individual variable (e.g. Basic Statistics, Correlation Analysis, Variability Structure, others), Integration Tools to explore the interaction of different variables and different datasets (e.g. Combined Parameters, Integration Assessment or Cross-Correlation Analysis, among others) and Advanced Integration Tools (e.g. coastal ocean adjustment to external forcings).

The Exploration Tools menu is to present available 2 options: the Extraction/Visualization, that allows the user to individually extract fields for a selected time or extract timesteps for a selected location; Basic Statistics, that allows the user to retrieve the Statistics for the Global Period. By selecting one of the variables presented, the available datasets (exported previously) are presented to the user. One or multiple choices of these datasets can be selected by the user, the analysis being developed for each one of these choices.

The user can then select the type of product that can be developed from the Basic Statistics option. A predefined option, that will be always produced, corresponds to the basic statistics for the complete time extension of the dataset. Two other options are to be added to the standard product. One corresponds to the basic statistics for predefined time periods. The user can choose either monthly statistics or weekly statistics or both. These options are only available if the length of the time series allows for the calculation of the statistics. The second option that the user can select corresponds to the basic statistics for a user-defined time period. In this case, the user is asked to provide the start time and the end time of the period to be analysed. The products built from the Basic Statistics option are to be presented to the user both in table format as well as in graph format.

The Integration Tools menu presents the possibility to analyze the Transport Pathway Trajectories of a Passive Tracer, defined as described in the previous section. Here the trajectories are calculated using NEMO daily fields and combining the NEMO fields with hourly HF radar data. In the menu, the user can select the initial date and time, and initial location of the drifter, both contained in the ranges defined in the initial user selection for time range and area of interest. The user clicks the Run Integration Results button and the download of the output files becomes available, as well as a button to Plot the Integration

Results. This opens a plot window, where the image can be analysed and downloaded. The Advanced Integration Tools menu is not available at this stage.

Figure 9. Integration Tools menu options to be filled in.

Pathway trajectories

Figure 10. Pathway trajectories example plot, showing results for NEMO and HFR.

3.5.2. How to identify extreme events impacts on coastal ocean areas of Europe

Thematic service 2 provides the users with a number of tools aimed to support the research on extreme events impacting the coastal ocean areas of Europe. The thematic service follows the same structure implemented for Thematic Service #1, described above. The users interface allows any user to select:

- the geographical area of interest (note that for a smoother experience, a maximum of 2 to 3 of the yellow areas highlighted should be selected);
- the extreme event, between Storm Emma, Hurricane Leslie and Storm Ophelia;
- the analysis option, between “Impacts on bottom sedimentary cover” and “Impacts on aquaculture installations”.

Figure 11. Dashboard for Thematic Service 2.

A number of datasets are made available in the Thematic Service, corresponding to EMODNet Bathymetric Data of the Iberian region, the correspondent EMODNet Bottom Sedimentary Cover Data, and the waves and currents data for the 3 extreme events indicated before, which includes pre-processed hourly fields of the main wave parameters from CMEMS WF-WAM Wave Model and hourly fields of barotropic current from CMEMS NEMO model.

Figure 12. Example of the selection of an area of interest, by the user, and available Advanced Analysis Options for the Integration Tools.

A choice of tools for the Advanced Analysis Options is then presented to the user, specifically both analysis options of “Impacts on bottom sedimentary cover” (type 1 analysis) and “Impacts on offshore structure” (aquaculture installations) (type 2 analysis). Following the user’s selection of the type of analysis, the selected analysis, from the 2 available, is performed, and a number of results are presented in file and graphical formats. The available graphical plots for the first analysis focus on the characterization of bottom shear stresses associated with currents, waves, combined effect of currents and waves, and critical shear stresses for remobilization. Water column velocity plots are made available for the second analysis option.

Figure 13. Wave Peak Period Direction & Barotropic Current plot examples.

3.5.3. How to process glider data

Thematic Service #3 (TS#3) provides a data processing toolbox and a viewer that facilitates the analysis of glider mission observations. TS#3 is based on the original Glider Transport Toolbox (see Section 8 of this document, in the references of VLab 1 section) developed by SOCIB and written in Matlab. This code has been migrated to Python language and generalized to handle various input glider data formats and broader geographical areas.

TS#3 consists of three main components, which are listed and described below:

- **Glider Converter** (pre-processing toolbox - cf. Sec. 3.5.3.2-3.5.3.7): this Python toolbox processes Slocum raw binary data to obtain an OG1.0 netCDF dataset. The input data is composed of the binary files generated by Slocum gliders. Users can upload these binary files in one single zip file. This toolbox is highly customizable and allows specifying various parameters to ensure the desired output.
- **Glider Postproc** (processing toolbox - cf. Sec. 3.5.8-3.5.12): This Python toolbox takes glider mission datasets in netCDF format and creates a detailed data product that includes a collection of static images and a netCDF grid dataset. The latter is formatted as an L2 dataset as defined in the advanced data product manual (more details can be found in Juza et al., 2025). In particular, it produces interpolated data on a regular grid (vertical section interpolated across a standard line

defined by the user) for potential temperature, salinity, density, and geostrophic velocity. The methodology from Juza et al. (2025) has been applied and implemented to compute geostrophic velocities derived from the hydrographic profiles.

- **TS#3 Data Viewer** (cf. Sec. 3.5.13): This visualization tool is accessible from the VLab home page and allows users to interactively explore the output generated by the Glider Postproc toolbox. Users need to insert the output files in the designated folder within their workspace to use the viewer.

In Sec. 3.5.3.1, it is described how to prepare the environment for the Glider Converter and the Glider Postproc.

3.5.3.1. Using the toolboxes in Thematic Service 3

Here is the detailed description of how to use the toolboxes included in the Thematic Service 3. The steps to be performed are:

- **Step 1:** Launch a new Jupyter Notebook (see figure below):
 - Click the “Jupyter Lab: Start” menu item of the JupyterHub menu;

Select the “ICOOE Thematic Service 3 (Jupyter Notebook) - 8 Cores / 32G RAM” and click the Start button.

Figure 14. Starting Thematic Service #3 JupyterHub

- **Step 2 (environment preparation):** copy the *resources* folder (available at [/workspace/VREFolders/ICOOE/TS3](#)) into the JupyterLab home directory.
 - The recommended way to copy the folder is: start a Terminal and make sure you are in your home directory, then execute: `cp -r workspace/VREFolders/ICOOE/TS3/resources .`
 - Two folders are included:
 - **OG10_templates:** this folder contains the json files needed for using the Glider Converter toolbox. These files are a starting point for configuring the processing of Slocum raw binary data. In particular, you can specify your own global attributes, glider, and sensor information as indicated in the OG1.0 format manual.
 - **Examples:** The folder contains notebooks that showcase how to use the toolboxes included in the TS#3. They can also be used as a starting point for your use cases. This folder also contains an `input_data` folder with a `tar.gz` file containing raw data files and metadata of a Slocum mission to test the **glider_converter** package.
 - We recommend not changing both folders' content but copying the needed files to develop your use cases.

3.5.3.2. Using the Glider Converter toolbox (v 0.3.0)

Start by examining the example in your home directory ($\$HOME/resources/examples$). To run the provided example, within the $examples/input_data$ folder, a tar.gz file is included. As a first step, you can *unzip* and extract the included files. The steps to be performed are as follows:

1. Open a Terminal and enter the directory: `cd $\$HOME/resources/examples/input_data$`
2. Run `tar xvzf raw_DT_glider_sdeep04_20171115_binary.tar.gz`
3. Optionally, you can delete the tar.gz file, as all included files have been created in the containing folder.

Then, you can run the provided example notebook by only updating the `input_path` argument to match the location of the input dataset in your workspace:

```
with GliderProcessor(
    input_path="resources/examples/input_data/raw_DT_glider_sdeep04_20171115_binary",
    platform_serial_number="sdeep04",
    glider_type=GliderType.SLOCUM_G2
) as gp:
    gp.do_process()
```

This example also relies on the content of the folder $\$HOME/resources/OG10_templates$. In the next section, a detailed description of this folder’s content is provided.

The service currently supports the following Slocum glider models: G1, G2, G3, G3, and G3S. These models can be specified through the `GliderType` Python enumeration:

```
SLOCUM_G1 = {
    "name": "Slocum G1",
    "url": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B76/current/B7600013",
}
SLOCUM_G2 = {
    "name": "Slocum G2",
    "url": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B76/current/B7600001",
}
SLOCUM_G3 = {
    "name": "Slocum G3",
    "url": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B76/current/B7600014",
}
```

```
}
SLOCUM_G3_SHALLOW = {
  "name": "Slocum G3 shallow",
  "url": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B76/current/B7600033",
}
SLOCUM_G3S = {
  "name": "Slocum G3S",
  "url": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B76/current/B7600029",
}
```

You should keep in mind that the tool takes between 5 and 30 minutes to process a glider mission, although the exact time may depend on both the size of the input dataset and the computing infrastructure itself.

Here is an example of typical output messages when processing a glider mission:

```
2025-07-10 07:33:21: ⚠ Please be aware that this process can take a while... You'll be informed as the process progresses. In addition, an extended log file will be available: glider_processor_20250710T073308.log
```

```
2025-07-10 07:33:21: 📧 Processing 199 sections in parallel...
```

```
2025-07-10 07:34:26: ✖ Error when processing section 2017-318-4-52: data section skipped. Processing will continue with next sections...
```

```
2025-07-10 07:34:49: ✖ Error when processing section 2017-318-4-69: data section skipped. Processing will continue with next sections...
```

```
2025-07-10 07:36:02: ✖ Error when processing section 2017-318-4-123: data section skipped. Processing will continue with next sections...
```

```
2025-07-10 07:36:33: ✖ Error when processing section 2017-318-4-148: data section skipped. Processing will continue with next sections...
```

```
2025-07-10 07:38:28: 📧 Sorting variables...
```

```
2025-07-10 07:38:31: 📧 Recalculating PROFILE_NUMBER...
```

```
2025-07-10 07:38:33: 📧 Interpolating missing values...
```

2025-07-10 07:38:37: Updating attributes...

2025-07-10 07:38:39: Trimming dataset data before 20171115T110000...

2025-07-10 07:38:40:

Done. Final output written to: output/sdeep04_20171115T110000_delayed.nc

2025-07-10 07:38:41: Elapsed time: 5.3 minutes.

Note that the output includes messages to inform the user that some glider sections might not be able to be processed (i.e., an ebd and dbd file might be missing, etc.) by the current toolbox. This may be normal, as some mission sections do not contain enough or valid data.

3.5.3.3. The Glider Converter Toolbox: description

The **Glider Converter Toolbox** is designed to produce **Ocean Glider format version 1.0** (OG1.0) from Slocum raw binary data. In the framework of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project (WP4), only sensor variables required by the **Glider Postproc Toolbox**, are currently generated and included in the OG1.0 format netCDF. The variables are:

- Sea water pressure
- Sea water temperature
- Sea water electrical conductivity
- Sea water practical salinity

In addition, the netCDF files generated by the toolbox follow the current version of the Ocean Glider format including all required metadata and variables.

To properly execute the toolbox, the following *json* files have to be included in the folder containing the raw binary files of the mission of interest.

3.5.3.4. Global attributes: metadata.json

The metadata.json file includes all required global attributes as well as some recommended attributes according to the OG1.0 specification. Please, follow the specification to include valid values for these attributes.

- `start_date`: this global attribute allows specifying (as a valid ISO 8601 value) the real start date and time of the mission. The toolbox will remove all previous data included in the raw files from the resulting netCDF.

3.5.3.5. Raw variables: `raw_variables.json`

The `raw_variables.json` file specifies a mapping between the variables included in the raw data files and the toolbox processing capabilities. This file **is not intended** to be updated by the user and is included only as a reference.

3.5.3.6. OG1.0 variables: `OG10_variables.json`

The `OG10_variables.json` file content allows the processing toolbox to generate the netCDF variables and its attributes according to the OG1.0 format. It can also include (in some cases) specific algorithms and parametrizations to process the data appropriately.

Users are expected to include specific information in this file:

- Values: through the "value" key included in some variables, users can specify metadata related to the glider mission being processed. Note that *null* values are managed by the toolbox, and thus, they are not expected to be filled manually in this *json* file. Currently, only these variable values have to be filled in the *json* file:
 - WMO_IDENTIFIER, DEPLOYMENT_LATITUDE, DEPLOYMENT_LONGITUDE.
- Sensor metadata variables: according to the OG1.0 specification, the sensor metadata is represented as variables. Users can include variables and their attributes in the *json* file so they can then be included in the resulting netCDF file. For instance:

```
"SENSOR_CTD_9771": {
  "sensor_type_vocabulary": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/130/",
  "long_name": "Sea-Bird CT Sail CTD",
  "sensor_model": "Sea-Bird CT Sail CTD",
  "sensor_model_vocabulary": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L22/current/TOOL1188/",
  "sensor_maker": "Sea-Bird Scientific",
  "sensor_maker_vocabulary": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L35/current/MAN0013/",
  "sensor_serial_number": "9771",
  "sensor_calibration_date": "",
  "value": "SENSOR_CTD_9771"
},
```

3.5.3.7. Input data layout

Input data corresponding to a glider mission is a folder with the following content:

```
my_mission_data/  
├── data/  
│   ├── *.cac  
│   ├── *.dbd  
│   └── *.ebd  
├── metadata.json  
├── raw_variables.json  
└── OG10_variables.json
```

Note that this folder has to be uploaded into the user workspace as a tar.gz file (eg. my_mission_data.tar.gz).

3.5.3.8. Using the Glider Postproc Toolbox (v0.31.0)

You can start by examining the examples in your home directory ($\$HOME/resources/examples$): these Jupyter Notebooks showcase how to use this processing toolbox. You can run these examples as they are. The output will be stored both in your $\$HOME/icooe_ts3_output$ directory and in the $\$HOME/workspace/icooe_ts3_output$. The second directory is where the **TS#3 Viewer** reads the different outputs. Please, check both the **TS#3 Viewer** by clicking on the *Thematic Service 3* button at the top, and the content of the output folder in your home directory.

Please, follow the Glider Postproc manual for developing your use cases.

3.5.3.9. Glider Postproc manual

To run the Glider Postproc toolbox, you must import the Python class **GliderAdvanceProduct** (as well as some ancillary classes) from the Python package **glider_postproc** included in the TS#3 Jupyter Notebook:

```
from glider_postproc import Section
from glider_postproc import GliderAdvanceProduct
from glider_postproc import GliderType
from glider_postproc import get_bathymetry_smith_sandwell,
get_bathymetry_EBATHY_Bed_g_gmt4
```

To process a glider mission dataset, first create an instance of the class and then invoke its method **process_mission_section**. Both the class constructor and its methods have several mandatory and optional arguments. Through the optional arguments, you can change the default behavior of the processing:

```
with
GliderAdvanceProduct(input_file="https://thredds.socib.es/thredds/dodsC/auv/glider/sdeep02-
scb_sgdeep002/L1/2012/dep0001_sdeep02_scb_sgdeep002_L1_2012-03-12_data_dt.nc",
                    glider_type=GliderType.SEA_GLIDER,
                    process_variables=var_info_SOCIB,
                    mission_name="SOCIB_ENL_Canales_Mar2012_sdeep02") as gp:

    gp.process_mission_section(section=section_ibiza_channel,
                              bathymetry=get_bathymetry_smith_sandwell,
                              smooth=24,
                              temperature_min_spike=10,
                              salinity_min_spike=35)
```

Note the **with** Python statement is required in order to load the input dataset (i.e. the glider mission of interest) and to prepare it for its processing. Inside the **with** block, you can execute several processings from the input dataset. Importantly, the use of the **with** statement ensures a consistent setup and cleanup of the process. An example of several processings from the same input dataset can be:

```
with GliderAdvanceProduct(input_file="input/sdeep04-qc20_20171115T110000_delayed.nc",
                          glider_type=GliderType.SLOCUM_G2,
                          mission_name="PARTHENOPE_EXT-
OG_ABACUS4_NOV2017_SDEEP04_GFMR0066_JERICO-NEXT-TNA") as gp:
```

```
gp.process_mission_section(section=section_argelian_bassin,  
                           bathymetry=get_bathymetry_smith_sandwell,  
                           smooth=24,  
                           temperature_min_spike=10,  
                           salinity_min_spike=35)
```

```
gp.variables['pressure'].apply_qc(4)  
gp.process_mission_section(section=section_argelian_bassin,  
                           bathymetry=get_bathymetry_smith_sandwell,  
                           smooth=24,  
                           temperature_min_spike=10,  
                           salinity_min_spike=35)
```

Note that in this example, the appropriate QC ancillary variable must be included in the input netCDF file.

Another example is based on applying a different min spike for temperature:

```
with GliderAdvanceProduct(input_file="input/sdeep04-qc20_20171115T110000_delayed.nc",  
                           glider_type=GliderType.SLOCUM_G2,  
                           mission_name="PARTHENOPE_EXT-  
OG_ABACUS4_NOV2017_SDEEP04_GFMR0066_JERICO-NEXT-TNA") as gp:
```

```
gp.process_mission_section(section=section_argelian_bassin,  
                           bathymetry=get_bathymetry_smith_sandwell,  
                           smooth=24,  
                           temperature_min_spike=10,  
                           salinity_min_spike=35)
```

```
gp.process_mission_section(section=section_argelian_bassin,  
                           bathymetry=get_bathymetry_smith_sandwell,  
                           smooth=24,  
                           temperature_min_spike=14,  
                           salinity_min_spike=35)
```

3.5.3.10. Mandatory arguments

a. GliderAdvancedProduct class constructor

In order to instantiate an object of this class, you may call its constructor. This class is mainly responsible for reading the input dataset. It also allows multiple processing operations without the need to read the input dataset. Note that a **with** Python statement **must** be used to wrap the constructor call. Mandatory and optional arguments are described next:

- **input_file**: this file specifies the input netCDF dataset. It can be an OPeNDAP URL, a path within the workspace, or a netCDF file uploaded from the user's local computer. For instance, one can generate a glider mission netCDF by means of the Glider Converter toolbox and use it as input for the Glider Postproc toolbox. URLs can be specified when there is public access to the OPeNDAP service of the related netCDF dataset.
- **glider_type**: it is necessary to specify the main glider model since the process toolbox may optimize the processing based on it. It can be specified through a Python enum `GliderType` with the following values: "SLOCUM_G1", "SLOCUM_G2", "SLOCUM_G3", "SEA_GLIDER".
- **mission_name** (mandatory): name of the mission without spaces. A folder with this exact name will be created within the `output_path` to store output files.

b. Process_mission_section instance method

To start processing the input dataset, you may call this method. This method is mainly responsible for processing the input dataset, based on the provided arguments. You can repeat the process inside the Python **with** statement by varying the arguments in each method call, as many times as you want. Each processing will produce, apart from the outputs, two *json* files: *processing.log* and *process_config.json*. The first one includes a detailed log of the processing, while the second one includes a full track of all arguments provided (both in the class constructor and in this method call). Both files can be found in the folder `log` inside the output folder (`$HOME/workspace/icooe_ts3_output`). Mandatory and optional arguments are described next:

- The "section" argument allows the user to specify the section of interest within the glider mission. The argument is an instance of the `Section` class.
- **smooth**: filter length scale (see Juza et al., 2025, for further details).
- **bathymetry** (mandatory): the name of the function that returns the bathymetry dataset used for the calculation. The function will accept a mandatory argument of type `Section` and must return a tuple of 3 elements, each of those being a valid 1D numpy array for x, y, and z (i.e., elevation or topography). Currently, 2 functions (datasets) are included in the `glider_postproc` package:
 - `get_bathymetry_smith_sandwell`

- get_bathymetry_EBATHY_Bed_g_gmt4: global EMODnet bathymetry.
- temperature_min_spike: minimum threshold value for temperature.
- salinity_min_spike: minimum threshold value for salinity.
- short_description: a short text that will facilitate exploration in the TS#3 Viewer. In addition, this text will be included in the generated plots to provide some context.

3.5.3.11. Optional arguments

a. GliderAdvancedProduct class constructor

The following arguments are not mandatory and allow customization of the default behavior of the Python class:

- process_variables: it consists of a Python dictionary to specify a map between the requested parameters needed by the **glider_postproc** toolbox and the parameters included in the input netCDF file. The user has to provide a map for each one of the following parameters: "profile_index", "profile_direction", "latitude", "longitude", "time", "pressure", "temperature" and "salinity". The values of the dictionary are instances of the **Parameter class** (see below), indicating in its constructor the corresponding parameter name of the input netCDF file. For instance: *variables = { ..., "temperature": Parameter("TEMP"), ... }*. Default value: the mapping with the OG1.0 format related parameters as it follows

```
{
  "profile_index":          OG.PROFILE_NUMBER.value,
  "profile_direction":     OG.PHASE.value,
  "latitude":              OG.LATITUDE.value,
  "longitude":             OG.LONGITUDE.value,
  "time":                  OG.TIME.value,
  "pressure":              OG.PRESSURE.value,
  "temperature":          OG.TEMPERATURE.value,
  "salinity":              OG.SALINITY.value,
}
```

The glider_postproc toolbox can process netCDF files expressed in the SOCIB format as the following example shows:

```
import Parameter as P
```

```

process_var_SOCIB = {
    "profile_index": Parametr("profile_index"),
    "profile_direction": SOCIB_PHASE,
    "latitude": P("latitude"),
    "longitude": P("longitude"),
    "time": P("time"),
    "pressure": P("pressure"),
    "temperature": P("temperature"),
    "salinity": P("salinity"),
}

```

When setting a custom mapping, it is important to access the parameters using the `variables` attribute of the main class (see Enrique Castrillo, the **Parameter** class section below).

b. Process_mission_section instance method

The following optional arguments allow customization of the Python method's default behavior:

- `long_description`: this text will provide further context and explanation of the processing. It will be shown in the TS#3 Viewer while exploring processing results.
- `bin_resolution_vert`: resolution of the vertical dimension (depth). Default value: 5.
- `bin_resolution_horiz`: resolution of the horizontal dimension (longitude in case of the Ibiza Channel). Default value: 2.
- `use_ref_vel`: flag for applying `ref_vel`. Default value: False.
- `ref_vel`: reference level velocity for GV calculation. Only taken into account if `use_ref_ver` is `True`. Default value: 0 (see Juza et al., 2025 for explanation).
- `dataset_qc`: It allows specifying QC thresholds that apply to the whole input dataset rather than to individual parameters. The QC is calculated when the original netCDF file has been converted into a set of vertical profiles as performed by the glider. A profile is considered valid only when it satisfies all the conditions imposed by the object passed to this parameter. Such an object must be an instance of the class **DatasetQC**. Invalid profiles are excluded from further calculations. The `glider_postproc` toolbox outputs the following message to indicate the number of valid profiles as follows: *"Profiles in mission (good/total): 1254/2521"*. The `DatasetQC` constructor accepts the following optional arguments:
 - `data_min`: minimum number of data points that a profile must have to be considered valid. A valid data point is one that has valid values (i.e. not NaNs) for each of the mandatory parameters. Default value: 10.

- `db_gap`: maximum allowed gap in the pressure array within a profile. Default value: 5.
- `min_length`: minimum size of the profile after applying all previous criteria. Default value: 20.

For instance:

```
from glider_postproc import DatasetQC
my_QC = DatasetQC(db_gap = 7)
```

3.5.3.12. Ancillary Python class

a. Section class

This class allows defining the section of interest within the glider mission. The following arguments can be accepted by the class constructor:

- `name`: name of the section. A folder with this name will be created within the *mission_name* the specific images related to the section.
- `lat_min`, `lat_max`, `lon_min`, `lon_max`: the bounding box defining the geographic area for processing. Data outside of this bounding box is ignored. Users are advised to set up this bounding box depending on what they consider the section of interest.
- `standard_line`: the horizontal line upon the actual glider trajectory is projected to perform all the calculations. For the geostrophy velocity compute, both UGOS and VGOS are calculated unless the standard line is strictly north-south (only UGOS is provided) or east-west (only VGOS is provided). The values are a tuple made of initial point and end point, being each point a tuple of longitude and latitude (eg. `standard_line=((39.795, 4.69), (39.795, 8.00))`).
- `lon_threshold_west`, `lon_threshold_east`: for repeated transects within one single section. Positions outside this longitude interval are ignored (e.g. glider's turning maneuver)
- `traj_map_bb`: bounding box of the map used for plotting the section trajectory (a 4-tuple like this: `lon_min, lon_max, lat_min, lat_max`)
- `bathy_max_depth`: maximum depth considered for calculations.

b. Parameter class

This class represents a data parameter for processing purposes. The constructor accepts one mandatory parameter to indicate the parameter name in the input netCDF file. In addition, it allows applying a data filter by calling the `apply_qc` method. Such a method shall only be called if the related parameter has an associated QC flag parameter in the input netCDF file. Otherwise an exception is thrown. The method accepts one single argument to indicate the QC threshold for filtering the data. When called with a

threshold, it masks data values below that threshold with NaNs. When called without arguments, it reverts to using all data values, regardless of QC flags.

Example:

```
temp_paramn = my_processing.variables['temperature'] # See default mapping for processing variables above.
```

```
temp_param.appy_qc(4) # Given that the appropriate QC param exists in the input netCDF file and it is linked to the PTEMP parameter as an ancillary variable, the parameter data whose QC flags are below 4 (e.g. "bad_data") is ignored (i.e. masked to NaNs) during the calculations.
```

```
temp_param.apply_qc() # Data is returned to its original state, all data values are considered for the calculations no matter the related QC flags.
```

c. Phase class

This class handles how the glider's phase (e.g. ascent, descent) is represented in the input netCDF file). This is essential for correct data processing: there are two specialized instances described below.

- SOCIB_PHASE instance
 - For SOCIB gliders only.
- PHASE_OG10 instance (default class)
 - Aimed for OG1.0 datasets only. This is based on what it is specified in the [OG1.0 format manual](#).

d. OG_param enum

A Python enumeration that contains the OG1.0 parameters (i.e. instances of the **Parameter** class) as defined in the [OG1.0 format manual](#) (i.e. parameter names as specified in the related vocabs). This enumeration can be used to define the list of parameters to be read from the input netCDF file (see example 5).

3.5.3.13. Viewer

The **Viewer** enables users to interactively explore and analyze advanced products generated from processed missions. Its design combines a hierarchical data selector (mission → processing date → transect) with an intuitive graphical interface for visualization and download of results (see figure below).

Figure 15. Thematic Service #3 Viewer

- Mission and Data Selection

Users begin by selecting the **mission** of interest, followed by the **processing date** and the specific **transect**. Notably, the **processing date** shows a short description of the processing to ease its identification in the dropdown list (see figure below). The system automatically loads the corresponding metadata and available graphics, including a general map with the glider trajectory and detected transects.

Figure 16. Thematic Service #3 Viewer

- Visualization of Oceanographic Variables

For each selected transect, the Viewer provides a collection of graphical representations of the main derived oceanographic variables:

- Potential temperature
- Salinity
- Potential density
- Geostrophic velocity (U component)
- Geostrophic velocity (V component)

Users can enable or disable variables through a dynamic button system, making it easy to compare parameters side by side. The plots are displayed in adaptive grids, and each image can be expanded, inspected in detail, and downloaded individually (see figure below).

Figure 17. Expanded plot showing for a specific variable in the Thematic Service #3 Viewer

- Navigation Across Transects

The interface integrates a carousel and a sliding tab system to move seamlessly between consecutive transects. Additionally, the Viewer preloads images from neighboring transects to optimize navigation and ensure a smooth user experience.

- General Mission Products

Besides, the Viewer also displays general mission-level products, such as the **map of all transects**. They provide a comprehensive overview of the mission.

- Processing Information Sidebar

A **collapsible right sidebar** can be expanded to reveal the **processing configuration** and metadata used to generate the products. This panel summarizes key inputs (e.g. source file, variables), dataset QC thresholds and processing parameters (binning, smoothing, reference velocity usage, geostrophic

settings, timestamps and output folders).

From this panel, users can:

- Download **the configuration** as a **JSON file** (for reproducibility and audit).
- Download **the processing log** (for traceability and troubleshooting).

Figure 18a. Access to process information in the Thematic Service #3 in the Viewer

Figure 18b. Thematic Service #3 process information detail

- [Product Download](#)

The Viewer offers several download options:

- Each image includes a button for individual saving.
- A main button at the bottom allows users to download the **complete Advanced Data Product** in NetCDF format, facilitating further analysis in external environments or long-term archiving.

3.6. Using other data sources

The different data sources that are used by VLab 1 are detailed in Section 3.3. Other additional data sources may include specific observations collected by members of the JERICO-RI community and are not yet available from data aggregators such as EMODnet or the European HF radar node. These are not included at the present stage. But the next step development of TS#2 (by the end of the project in June 2026) is planned to include data from multiparametric buoys operated by JERICO partners (as part of the data sets associated with each storm). And TS#1 can be updated for, in the future, to search other data providers (e.g. institutional webpages or JERICO portal). A more advanced step, involving the use of data provided directly by the users, can also be incorporated in future developments of these two Thematic Services. Importantly, TS#3 is designed to operate on user-provided input data, which must be uploaded to the user workspace. This input may consist of Slocum raw binary data from a single mission, or of data already processed into a standard format (preferably OG1.0 or an equivalent representation). In the former case, the user works directly with the raw files downloaded from the glider platform at the end of a mission. In the latter case, the user is responsible for identifying and obtaining suitable input data from appropriate data repositories. The Python libraries provided by TS#3 include utilities to map the original repository-specific formats to the format required by the post-processing Python library (see the relevant how-to section for further details).

4. Introduction to VLab 2 “Coastal Currents from Observations”

This section is authored by Abel Dechenne, Alexander Barth (Université de Liège) and Igor Ruiz Atake (CMCC Foundation - Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate).

The VLab 2 called “Coastal Currents from Observations” aims to show a multi-source approach framework to study and reconstruct surface currents through a variational inverse method: Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions (DIVAnd). It is presented as a Jupyter notebook and written in Julia language. As an initial test case, users might also use WITOIL to perform oil spill simulations from the generated datasets.

The current approach aims to reconstruct Mediterranean surface currents with monthly surface currents at the basin scale.

Three types of data are considered for the approach:

- **Surface drifters** (essential for the cross validation framework);
- **Satellite altimetry** (dataset with a high spatial and temporal coverage used to derive geostrophic currents);

- **High Frequency (HF) Radars.**

4.1 Target Users & Community

For the Coastal Currents VLab, target users are scientists in the field of oceanography. It is known that surface currents are involved in the upper layer dynamical processes and are thus important for several applications. The most likely community to use our products are modelers that need to force surface currents for their analysis or for validation of hydrodynamical models. As an example, the MEDSLIK-II model built by [Euro-Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change \(CMCC\)](#) researchers will take our product as a forcing variable to forecast the oil spill model.

These results will also be helpful to understand the seasonality and the interannual variability in surface currents for the Mediterranean Sea. Another use could be an educational use to teach students about reconstruction of data in oceanography and to showcase an “interpolation” technique.

4.2 State of art

Sea surface currents (SSC) are central for understanding ocean upper dynamics and interactions. Indeed, currents transport heat, mass, create conditions for up- or downwelling systems and drive the content of the primary variables such as oxygen and chlorophyll. Thus, SSC is an important factor that conditions primary production and therefore, the whole biological interaction of the trophic chain. Surface currents also play a central role in dispersion of pollutants, for example in the case of oil spill models. Due to this, SSC are part of the **Essentials Ocean Variables (EOVs)** (as defined by Global Ocean Observing System community), which confirms their importance to oceanography knowledge and research. As a consequence, analysis over large timescales at basin scale are precious for capturing variability and recurrent patterns of circulation.

However, direct SSC measurements are sparse, especially at the scale of a basin. Due to this issue, we need to find a way to get complete gridded files, as they are used to force models or to predict dispersion of pollutants. To overcome this problem, researchers often use interpolation techniques to fill the gaps.

We propose here to bring a new way to combine indirect remote sensing data and direct in-situ observation to obtain a reconstructed gridded surface currents dataset.

The variational inverse method is called **Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions (DIVAnd)** and is based on a cost function which will penalize abrupt gradients in the analyses. The approach also considers dynamic constraints which are added to the cost function. We consider the

presence of the coastline, the generally small horizontal divergence and the surface pressure gradient.

4.3 Input data sources

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
Altimetry	CMEMS dataset: SEALEVEL_EUR_PHY_L3_MY_008_061	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEALEVEL_EUR_PHY_L3_MY_008_061/description
Sea Surface Current (drifters)	CMEMS dataset: INSITU_GLO_PHY_UV_DISCRETE_MY_013_044	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/INSITU_GLO_PHY_UV_DISCRETE_MY_013_044/description
High Frequency Radars	CMEMS dataset: INSITU_GLO_PHY_UV_DISCRETE_MY_013_044	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/INSITU_GLO_PHY_UV_DISCRETE_MY_013_044/description

Table 2. VLab 2 Input data sources

4.4. VLab availability

This VLab is available through Blue-Cloud gateway at : <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/coastalcurrentsfromobservations>

4.5. Step by step guideline to use the VLab

This step by step guide will describe how to use the VLab for the following activities:

- How to set up the user-specific working environment (cf. Sec. 4.5.1);
- How to use the Coastal Currents Main Notebook (cf. Sec. 4.5.2);
- How to run an oil spill simulation (cf. Sec. 4.5.3).

4.5.1. How to set up the working environment

Similarly to any VLab, a user must register in the Blue-Cloud VRE, log in, and access the Coastal Currents From Observation via the menu (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Blue-Cloud VRE Home page

When entering in the VLab (Figure 20), the user faces a number of services and facilities. In particular, the user is provided with JupyterLab, which can be launched by either using the specific app box or the VLab menu “Analytics”

Figure 20. VLab 2 Homepage

Once in the JupyterLab, use the file browser (Fig. 21, the left part) to select the following directory

~/workspace/VREFolders/CoastalCurrentsFromObservations/

Then open the notebook “Install_Vlab2.ipynb” and run it. This notebook will set up the environment to run the main code for the VLab and install the required dataset.

Please note that this notebook has to be run with the latest Julia version available, by selecting the kernel on top right of the notebook. Once this notebook is run, a new folder named “CoastalCurrents” is created in which we find the main notebook in the folder “example”, and the datasets in the folder “tmp”.

Figure 21. VLab 2 JupyterLab Homepage

4.5.2. How to use the Coastal Currents Main Notebook

The Installation notebook created the user working directory which contains the dataset, the dependencies and the main codes, found in the folder “example”

In “example”, we find the main notebook : **Surface_Currents_Main.ipynb**

The notebook can be run cell-by-cell, **by pressing enter + shift.**

The code contains three different sections.

- 1) Data visualization;
- 2) DIVAnd interpolation, accompanied by the RMS error related to each month;

- 3) Validation and plot of the results (Validation regression lines, maps of validation, interpolated surface currents and physical parameters of the analysis).

Useful functions

(stored in ~/CoastalCurrents/src/)

- [CoastalCurrents.jl](#), [Altimetry.jl](#) and [hfradar.jl](#) are used for their **loaddata()** functions which are used inside of "[data_preparation.jl](#)". It stores variables in vectors for computing facilities.
- [Plotting.jl](#) is useful for **CoastalCurrents.Plotting.plotmap(bathname)** which adds the mask on results maps.
- [nc2leafletvelocities.jl](#) is used to get dynamical outputs of the surface currents.

1) How to access the dataset

(stored in ~/tmp/BlueCloud2026/)

- Three folders are present there; Altimetry, Drifters and HF Radars in separate directories.
- In a separate file we find bathymetry and mask file "gebco_30sec_4.nc". This file is downloaded automatically if it is not done yet.

If you want to download the dataset to build locally the same environment, "right click" on the dataset and then select "download".

Resolution and boundaries of the analysis are tuned in ~/CoastalCurrents/examples/common.jl (Figure 21).

To do so:

- lonmax (maximum longitude), lonmin (minimum longitude), latmax (maximum latitude), latmin (minimum latitude) are set.
- The resolution is given by dlon and dlat (in arc degrees).
- For squared gridded output, dlon = dlat.

```

8 # Grid definition
9 lonmax = 37
10 lonmin = -7
11 latmax = 46
12 latmin = 30
13
14 # resolution
15 dlon = dlat = 0.25 # Resolution
16 lonr = lonmin:dlon:lonmax # -7 Gibraltar to 37 which is BlackSea east
17 latr = latmin:dlat:latmax # 30 on Lybia to 46 onto the north of the Black Sea
18

```

Figure 21. Resolution and boundaries composition

To load the mask, “gebco_30sec_4.nc” is used. It is downloaded automatically when running `include(“common.jl”)`.

In “`common.jl`”, we find:

```

23 # Base Directory for Dataset
24
25 basedir = expanduser("~/tmp/BlueCloud2026")
26
27 # Mask and bathymetry in basedir
28
29 bathname = joinpath(basedir,"gebco_30sec_4.nc")
30 bathisglobal = true
31

```

Figure 22. Load the mask

Which set “`bathname`” and “`bathisglobal`”. Main variables to load the mask (Figure 22). Then, in “`Surface Currents Main.ibynb`” we find (Figure 23):

Define the mask and necessary variables for interpolation

```

[44]: # Mask Loading
# bathname & bathisgoal are defined in common.jl

mask, (pm,pn), (xi,yi) = DIVAnd.domain(bathname,bathisglobal,lonr,latr)
mask = DIVAnd.floodfill(mask) .== 1
hx, hy, h = DIVAnd.load_bath(bathname, bathisglobal, lonr, latr);

# Trick of sea removing to avoid mistakes
mask[:,end] .= 0;
mask[:,end-1] .= 0;

```

Figure 23. Define the mask

Which sets the mask from bathname, bathisgoal and (lonr,latr), defined in “3) Resolution and boundaries”.

(pm,pn), (hx,hy,h) are derived from the mask and are used in **DIVAndrun_HFRadar()**.

DIVAndrun_HFRadar() which is the function used for DIVAnd method for currents and is run in the file “parm to rms.jl” which runs for each month.

This function need the following parameters (Figure 24);

- mask (Computed with **DIVAnd.domain()**, which is a 2d matrix fulfilled by 0 and 1)
- h (Bathymetry, computed with **DIVAnd.load_bath()**) in meters
- pm,pn (pm pn are parameters computed from the mask) inverse of the resolution (m^{-1})
- xi,yi (interpolated grid in degrees)
- x_tot,y_tot (observations locations in degrees)
- robs (the radial velocity or a single velocity component in m/s)
- directionobs_tot (direction vector computed from u & v in degrees)
- len (correlation length, which tune how far an observation can be interpolated)

```

112 #####
113 #                               DIVAnd run : HFRadar
114 #####
115
116
117 # Month per month : DIVAnd Interpolation
118
119 for i in 1 : 12
120
121 uri[:, :, i], vri[:, :, i], ni[:, :, i] = DIVAndrun_HFRadar(
122 mask, h, (pm, pn), (xi, yi), (x_tot[i], y_tot[i]), robs_tot[i], directionobs_tot[i], len, epsilon2[i];
123 eps2_boundary_constraint = eps2_boundary_constraint,
124 eps2_div_constraint = eps2_div_constraint,
125 # eps2_Coriolis_constraint = -1,
126 # f = 0.001,
127 # residual = residual,
128 # g = g,
129 # ratio = 100,
130 # lenq = (000.0, 000.0, 24 * 60 * 60. * 10),
131 # maxit = 100000,
132 # tol = 1e-6,
133 );
134
135     if i == 1
136         println("Si er mois claculé")
137     else
138         println("Si eme mois claculé")
139     end
140 end
141

```

Figure 24. Interpolation function “DIVAndrun_HFRadar” with the input variables and uri,vri and etai, the three dimensions outputs (lon, lat, time)

- epsilon2 (error variance of observations, which set the accuracy of the different dataset)

It returns:

- u and v velocities for the interpolated field (in m/s).
- Sea surface height of the region.

More information is provided at https://gher-uliege.github.io/DIVAnd_HFRadar.jl/dev.

The function stores the results, and these last are used for the following section;

- Validation with independent drifters
- Dataset visualization
- Physical parameters computation and visualization

Figure 25. Main results of the VLab. From top left to bottom: Validation of the results with independent drifters; Surface currents at the basin scale; Total kinetic energy computed at the basin scale.

2) How to correct a model with the results

The model correction is performed by running “Correction_CMCC_y.ipynb” which is in the example folder. Once again, this is runned simply by pressing “enter + tab” in each cell.

This code uses the results stored by running the main code “Surface_Currents_main.ipynb”. Then the surface currents of the physical model “Mediterranean Sea Physics Reanalysis” is downloaded for a year and will be corrected based on the interpolated observations.

Corrections steps:

- 1) CMEMS model is downloaded: Model
- 2) The model is averaged per month
- 3) Daily anomalies relative to the monthly mean will be computed
- 4) DIVAnd results will be loaded: Observations (this step cannot run if you did not followed the first steps at least once)
- 5) Observations are regridded based on the model
- 6) The added value of the observations is computed with : (Observations - Model = Added value) for each month
- 7) Then the added value is added to the model day by day to correct it
- 8) Last, the validation is performed on the corrected model and then model itself. The validation metrics are the same as for the first interpolation
- 9) Last, the results are saved and used within witoil.

Figure 26. Results for the model correction. The upper two figures show the validation of the model corrected with DIVAnd surface currents. The bottom two figures show the same validation procedure without correcting the model.

4.5.3. Use case: How to run an oil spill simulation from using DIVAnd run

In the main page of the VLab, click on Oil Spill Simulation and then “Start WITOIL” (cf. Fig. 27).

Figure 27. Start Oil Spill simulation

After clicking on Start WITOIL, a new page appears asking the user to launch the server. After this command is prompted, the platform will process the request and generate the webapp. The application starts on a landing page with information about the service and more information can be obtained by clicking on “**Before you Simulate**”, on the left hand side panel. When ready, proceed to WITOIL Simulation.

Figure 28. WITOIL landing Page

If the user has successfully run a simulation with DIVAnd and wrote the outputs correctly to `~/home/joyvan/WITOIL/`, when in the WITOIL Simulation page, the map in the application will have a blue box indicating the bounding box of the currents dataset, which are fundamental to perform an oil spill simulation. If desired, the user might run simulations using Copernicus Marine Services datasets, but then it is required to select **“No”** in the **“Use HFR Currents question”**. In this tutorial we will focus as if the user has selected to use the DIVAnd outputs.

Figure 29. WITOIL map selection for simulation with DIVAnd

The first action needed from the user is to select a single location within the blue box. In order to do that, the user should click on the location pin at the left-hand side of the map. Then it is just needed to click in the location (obviously at sea), and the application will provide the precise coordinates (Longitude and Latitude) of this point.

Figure 30. Example of Simulation Setup

The fields the user is expected to change are:

- **Available Dates:** The specific dates for which environmental data (currents) are available.
- **Spill hour:** The exact UTC hour at which the oil spill event begins.
- **Simulation Length:** The total runtime of the model in hours (maximum limit: 96 hours).
- **Oil API:** The American Petroleum Institute gravity index, representing the oil's density.
- **Oil Volume (Tonnes):** The total mass of oil released into the environment, measured in metric tonnes.
- **Spill Duration:** Set to 0 for a single burst (instantaneous) or specify hours for a continuous leak.
- **CDS Token:** Personal API key required to authenticate and download ECMWF climate data.
- **Simulation Name:** A unique alphanumeric identifier or label for the simulation run.

After all the inputs are provided, the simulation will start and the logs will inform the user when the simulation should be finished. Once it is done, the user can once again click on the left hand side panel in the **Results** tab to navigate to the simulation results.

In the Results page, the user can select from all of their simulation results stored in the workspace and visualize them according to the standard plot procedures provided by the WITOIL for Blue-Cloud application.

A self-paced training course for this VLab is available for free on the OceanTeacher Global Academy platform: <https://oceanexpert.org/event/4857> .

4.6. Using other data sources

Using other data sources is not automatized on this VLab. However, following the resolution, domain definition and data storage, the user might be able to change the region and the resolution.

5. Introduction to VLab 3 “Carbon-Plankton Dynamics”

This section is authored by Steven Pint, Cyrielle Delvenne, Tom Van Engeland, Gert Everaert, Thanos Gkritzalis (Flanders Marine Institute) and Matteo Bazarro, Michele Giani, Gianpiero Cossarini (National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics).

This VLab provides a workflow to run **mechanistic models** of the NPZD-type (Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton-Detritus), using near real-time data to quantify the relative contributions of the bottom-up and top-down drivers in phytoplankton dynamics. The NPZD models are commonly used, and describe four ecosystem components: nutrients, phytoplankton, zooplankton, and detritus with varying levels of detail. Two models are implemented: (1) a NPZD model with fixed elemental ratios, adjusted from the NPZD model of *Soetaert and Herman (2009)* and *Otero et al. (2023)*, hereafter termed basic NPZD model, and (2) a quota-type of NPZD model, based on the work by *Geider et al. (1998)*, extended with different organic matter pools after *Schartau et al. (2007)*. Hereafter termed extended NPZD model. Both models resolve parts of the carbon and nitrogen cycle. The basic model is used to demonstrate a workflow for assessing model uncertainty. The extended model is conceived as a demo version to look at parameter sensitivity in an interactive way.

In the basic model phytoplankton dynamics are simulated based on information from nutrient concentrations and zooplankton density. Based on these simulations using near real-time data, it is possible to calculate and visualize the relative contribution of each bottom-up or top-down driver, i.e. (1) nutrients, (2) Sea Surface Temperature (SST), (3) photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and (4) zooplankton grazing, over time (Figure 31). Carbon dynamics are simulated based on the marine biological carbon pump (Figure 31). The carbon pump in marine ecosystems operates as a key mechanism for carbon

dynamics. During photosynthesis, the phytoplankton captures carbon from the atmosphere, converting it into organic matter in the pelagic food web. This carbon is then transported downward as plankton and other organic material die and sink, forming detritus. As the detritus descends through the water column, it undergoes decomposition and remineralization, releasing carbon back into the water as Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC). This process not only regulates the distribution of carbon in the ocean but also plays a critical role in the global carbon cycle.

Figure 31. Visualization of the Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton-Detritus (NPZD) model.

The validation of the model is performed by comparing the model predictions, e.g. phyto- and zooplankton biomass, with field observations. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is calculated between prediction values and observational values. By doing so and by running the model for multiple parameterizations, we can select the best 10% simulations (lowest RMSE) to predict phyto- and zooplankton, and carbon dynamics and define confidence intervals around the model predictions. To

estimate the relative contributions of the drivers, we use these best 10% simulations, or select the best 5% simulations (based on the RMSE) to decrease computational effort.

The extended NPZD model resolves a water column and a rudimentary bottom in one vertical dimension (Figure 32). Two nutrient compartments exist for (1) reduced inorganic nitrogen (state variable: NH_4) and (2) oxidised inorganic nitrogen (state variable: NO_3).

Figure 32. Graphical representation of the structure of the extended NPZD model.

Two phytoplankton groups take up nitrogen from these pools with variable C/N ratios. Both phytoplankton groups are grazed by a zooplankton compartment. In contrast to the phytoplankton, the zooplankton has a fixed C/N ratio. Phytoplankton also produces dissolved organic matter through leakage

and active exudation. The dissolved organic carbon is in the model split up into a carbohydrate and a non-carbohydrate fraction (following *Schartau et al. 2007*), where the carbohydrate fraction is involved in the formation of marine snow (transparent exopolymeric particles, or TEP). This sinks to the bottom and is continuously remineralized. Phytoplankton and zooplankton that die enters a particulate detritus pool. This detritus nitrogen and carbon sinks to the bottom and is continuously broken down to form dissolved organic matter. Remineralization of this dissolved organic material occurs through oxic remineralization, anoxic remineralization, and denitrification. Since the presence of oxygen is a regulatory factor in these remineralization processes, it is also explicitly modelled as a state variable. The relationships between oxygen production and carbon fixation, and between oxygen consumption and all respiratory and remineralization processes are implemented with fixed elemental ratios. Oxygen and CO₂ are taken up by the sea from the atmosphere. Atmosphere-ocean gas exchange is modelled with gas transfer functions based on the work by Wanninkhof (*Wanninkhof 2014*). CO₂ that enters the model through the ocean surface enters a DIC pool and will modify the acid-base equilibrium. To calculate the acid-base equilibrium, total alkalinity (TA) and DIC are both included as state variables. The pH at the surface is implemented as a derived variable. A full description of the model is available in the R-package that contains the model and is accessible from the R-Studio server (see below).

The model is implemented as a Fortran program in an add-on package for the R Statistical Software (R Core Team, 2024). The Fortran program is called from an R function that accepts a number input datasets. These are in detail described in the help files and vignettes of the package. A web interface is callable from within the R-package (cf. help files). This web application allows for 'on-the-fly' interaction with the model (Figure 32). A choice can be made for a simple 0D box model version or a 1D vertically resolved model version (as described above). Model output is plotted against a background of data from the Dutch national monitoring program of Rijkswaterstaat, for which the data can also be obtained through **their web services**. A choice can be made from a selection of stations. Model simulations always start from 2001 and run for a number of years, selectable in the web application.

5.1. Target Users & Community

The target users of this VLab are researchers who are at the forefront of coastal ecosystem studies. The models are particularly well-suited for researchers that want to extend their activities into the field of ecosystem modeling or for educational purposes (i.e. to educate students interested in marine ecology). In such contexts, the models can be used either as a starting point for model development or as a demo on how to work with ecosystem models of low to moderate complexity.

In addition, the models present a view on the role of various biological compartments in carbon dynamics of coastal ecosystems. Once calibrated and validated, the models can simulate different scenarios and assess the effect on the carbon system and the marine ecosystem. In this context, they may be useful as analysis tools for researchers to reflect on processes that they deem responsible for patterns in their own data. The models could be useful as components of a Digital Twin for the Ocean.

5.2. State of art

Achieving a comprehensive characterization of phytoplankton, the basis of the marine food webs, requires multidisciplinary data. These use cases demonstrate how to link and integrate different data types (biology, biogeochemistry, and physics), available from several Blue-Cloud data infrastructures, and made interoperable through a Blue-Cloud Vlab, to run a mechanistic model identifying the drivers of phytoplankton abundance, and a machine-learning algorithm to calculate carbon sequestration.

Data on long-term zooplankton and phytoplankton observations, accessible from EMODnet Biology through the Discovery and Data Access and Service (DDA&S) were used in combination with carbon data from ICOS and SOCAT, and environmental data such as sea surface temperature and nutrient regimes from EMODnet Chemistry and other available data resources. Such heterogeneous data, in their nature and acquisition mode, cannot be combined and exploited in a straightforward manner. The data was used to detect and explain anomalies in long-term trends and quantify the relative contribution of the environmental drivers for these plankton essential ocean variables (EOVs). Coupling these systems allows testing the operational situation and assessing gap-filling or potential capabilities. The models could be used in the future to simulate different scenarios and assess the effect on the carbonate system and the marine ecosystem.

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
Zooplankton abundances	EMODnet Biology	Blue Cloud (VRE or DD&AS)
Phytoplankton proxy (Chla)	EMODnet Biology	Blue Cloud (VRE or DD&AS)
Abiotic data (nutrients, PAR, temperature, salinity, pH and carbon)	EMODnet chemistry SOCAT ICOS	Blue Cloud (VRE or DD&AS)
Biogeochemical data for the extended NPZD model	Rijkswaterstaat, Waterinfo	https://waterinfo.rws.nl Subset for the model demo webapp available in the NorthSeaCarbon R-package
PAR and wind data for the extended NPZD model	Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI)	https://www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/klimatologie/gemeten-reeksen Subset for the model demo webapp available in the NorthSeaCarbon R-package

5.3. Input data sources

Table 3. VLab 3 Input data sources

5.4. VLab availability

This VLab is available through the Blue-Cloud gateway at : <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/carbonplanktondynamics>

It is also available in the EDITO platform at <https://dive.edito.eu/training> (Demonstrator Carbon Plankton Dynamics).

5.5. Step by step guideline to use the VLab

This step by step guide describes how to use the VLab for the following activities:

- How to run the NPZD model (cf. Sec. 5.5.1);
- How to run the extended NPZD model (cf. Sec. 5.5.2);

A self-paced training course for this VLab is available for free on the OceanTeacher Global Academy platform: <https://oceanexpert.org/event/4858> .

5.5.1 The basic NPZD model

Before starting the model, there are requirements that need to be fulfilled. First of all, input data, such as nutrients, temperature, salinity, pH, wind and carbon data, are needed covering at least three years. The three-year period is needed to obtain daily data using generalized additive modelling. The daily data is used to run the model on daily time steps. Further, you need the Jupyter Notebook and accompanying R scripts. The Jupyter Notebook and R scripts are provided for you. Additionally, input data for the Belgian part of the North Sea and Gulf of Trieste are provided as well as demo. It is advised to have a basic understanding of R to run the NPZD model in R.

The workflow to use the basic NPZD model is provided in a Jupyter Notebook and contains the required information to run the model. When loading a Jupyter Notebook in the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) with the required R packages pre-installed (Blue-Cloud Carbon-Plankton Server - 8 Cores / 64G RAM), this document will be available in your *Home* folder. This Jupyter Notebook document contains all necessary information and code to (1) (re)calibrate the NPZD model, (2) simulate phyto- and zooplankton dynamics, (3) validate modeling results with observational data, (4) calculate the relative contribution of the bottom-up and top-down drivers on phytoplankton dynamics and (5) visualize the modeling results. The NPZD model runs in terms of nitrogen, as well as in terms of carbon.

Steps to run the Jupyter Notebook:

To aid in having all required documents in your *Homespace*, a Jupyter Notebook *setup-NPZD-model.ipynb* is provided in the *VRE folders/CarbonPlanktonDynamics*. Please copy this folder to your personal *workspace* by following the steps below.

1. Click on the *workspace* icon to go to the *workspace* (Figure 33).

Figure 33. VLab 3 workspace

- Open the *CarbonPlanktonDynamics* folder, right-click on the *setup-NPZD-model.ipynb* file and select make a copy (Figure 34).

Figure 34. Make a copy of the setup file

- Now, a copy appeared in the folder. You can move this copy of the setup file by clicking on the *Copy of setup-NPZD-model.ipynb* file, then click on move at the top. A screen will pop up where you click on your *workspace* symbol and click on move (Figure 35).

Figure 35. Move the copied setup file to your workspace

- Go back to the home page of the VLab and open the Jupyter Notebook from your CarbonPlanktonDynamics VRE homepage (Figure 36) and select the *Blue-Cloud Carbon-Plankton Server - 8 Cores / 64G RAM*. This server has the required R packages pre-installed.

Figure 36. Open Jupyter Notebook from your CarbonPlanktonDynamics VRE homepage

- Now, you should see the copied file in the column on the right of the screen (Figure 37). Double-click on it to open the file. If you run the code in the notebook, the Jupyter Notebook to run the NPZD model will be copied from the VRE folder to your Homespace and the required files to run it in the folder called NPZD. These should now be visible in the column on the left after clicking on the folder icon next to `/workspace/`.

Figure 37. Run the NPZD model

Steps to run the NPZD model:

1. If JupyterHub is not open already, open Jupyter Notebook from your CarbonPlanktonDynamics VRE homepage (Figure 38) and select the *Blue-Cloud Carbon-Plankton Server - 8 Cores / 64G RAM*. This server has the required R packages pre-installed.

Figure 38. Carbon Plankton Dynamics VRE Homepage

2. This will open a new tab in your browser where *JupyterLab* is launched (Figure 39). In the launcher, you now see two folders and a Jupyter Notebook in the column on the left of the screen. Select the *Jupyter Notebook* 'NPZD.ipynb'. This is the only document that you need to run the NPZD model with examples of the Belgian part of the North Sea (BPNS) or the northern Adriatic Sea. The *NPZD folder* contains the necessary files to run the NPZD model, such as .csv files and R scripts. The *workspace folder* is your personal folder where you can store your results. At the end of the Jupyter Notebook is a section where you can copy your results to your personal workspace.

Figure 39. Jupyter notebook ‘NPZD.ipynb’

3. Now, you can go through the Jupyter Notebook and run the model step by step following the instructions in the document with your input data (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Model manual

Below we provide Figure 41 showing a potential output of the model for the nearshore region of the BPNS, where the relative contributions of each of the drivers in phytoplankton abundances is illustrated.

Figure 41. Average monthly relative contributions for each limitation factor in the growth of phytoplankton for the nearshore region.

5.5.2 The extended NPZD model

The extended NPZD model is implemented as an add-on package, called NorthSeaCarbon, for the R Statistical Software. When a R-Studio server session is started up, the package is available in the package library and can be loaded from the R console in the usual way by typing `require(NorthSeaCarbon)`. To call the help-file of the model, type `?NSC1D` (the name of the function that accepts all inputs to the model and calls the appropriate model integration routines). A general introductory help page can be loaded by typing `?`NorthSeaCarbon-package``. The latter is a good starting point to explore the package. To start up the demo web application, type `PlayModel()` on the R console. A browser window will be opened (Figure 42).

Figure 42. The initial browser window after starting up the web application with the model demo.

The application has two tabs. The 'Model Explorer' tab contains the actual graphical interface to control the model. The 'Info' tab gives a full description of the model. The content of this tab is also available as a package vignette in the NorthSeaCarbon package, which is called from the R-console by typing `vignette("NSCmodel")`. In the upper right-hand corner a button with a question mark gives access to a help page explaining how to use the interface.

5.6. Using other data sources

Some requirements as discussed in 5.5.1 need to be fulfilled to run the NPZD models with other data. For the basic NPZD model, the time series of the input data should cover at least three years. These three years are needed to create daily data using interpolation methods such as Generalized Additive Models (GAM) or Generalized Linear Models (GLM) to obtain a complete set of input data. There are scripts available that can help prepare daily input data for other regions.

To use the model with data from regions other than the Belgian or Adriatic, it is recommended to obtain the necessary data from EMODnet, as the model is designed to work with this data source. Using data from other regions or sources may lead to errors, primarily due to differences in column names. To

minimize potential issues, refer to the input data provided for the Adriatic region as a guide when working with EMODnet data from other regions.

For the extended NPZD model more elaborate preparations are required before the model can be run with other data. It is important to note that the web interface only works with the built-in data structures, and only allows for selecting between different built-in datasets and for changing parameters. If the model is required to run with different input data, this is only possible with scripts in the BlueCloud R-Studio Server. Broadly speaking, forcing functions should be supplied as 2-column matrices which enter the NSC-function as function parameters. Model parameters should be supplied as a named list or vector. Default model grids are available in the package but can be altered as function parameters to the NSC-function as well. We refer to the help files ("`?`NorthSeaCarbon-package``" and references therein) for complete definitions of the requirements for the input data structures.

6. Introduction to VLab 4 “Marine Environmental Indicators”

The Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab enables users to monitor and evaluate the environmental conditions of marine areas, providing essential support for decision-making in ocean management. By integrating multiple data sources, the platform offers a unified data analysis service, facilitating online computation of indicators through Jupyter Notebooks or a dedicated web application. This application leverages the VRE Analytics Engine services to generate indicator outputs. This VLab 4 users handbook will be divided into five sections representing each indicator (OHC, TRIX, MHW, SSI v2) and the web application. Each of the indicators has its own state of art, input data sources and how-to section to better understand the scope of each. A [video tutorial](#) on how to access the VLab and its indicators can be found on the [Blue-Cloud Youtube Channel](#). This VLab is available through Blue-Cloud gateway at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/marineenvironmentalindicators> .

6.1. Target Users & Community

VLab 4 is designed for a wide range of users involved in marine research and environmental management. Key user groups include:

- **Environmental Scientists & Researchers:** Those focusing on marine ecosystems, oceanography, environmental and climate monitoring.
- **Policy Makers & Marine Resource Managers:** Users seeking insights for informed decision-making in marine and coastal resource management.

- **NGOs & Environmental Advocacy Groups:** Organizations working on marine conservation and sustainability initiatives.
- **Academic Institutions & Universities:** Research groups focusing on marine science and environmental protection.
- **General Public & Educational Institutions:** Those interested in understanding marine environmental issues through accessible data.

6.2. How to use the Jupyter Notebooks in the Vlab

Jupyter Notebooks are available for generating the different environmental indicators. Each notebook is self-explanatory and guides the user through its execution and customization to meet specific needs. Users can modify parameters such as the time range or the geographical region to be analyzed.

To access one of these notebooks, follow the instructions below.

These steps are tailored for the MHW notebook but can be easily adapted to others using the information provided in the table below:

1. Open the VLab at the address (Figure 43): <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/marineenvironmentalindicators>

Figure 43. Welcome page of VLab 4

2. Open a **JupyterLab** instance by selecting the **JupyterHub** tab inside the VRE VLab.
3. Open a terminal in JupyterHub by navigating to **File > New > Terminal** (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Open a JupyterHub terminal

- In the terminal, **copy the archive** in your own space on JupyterHub and **unzip it** using the following commands:

```
cp /workspace/VREFolders/MarineEnvironmentalIndicators/notebooks/MarineHeatWaves/MHW.zip .
unzip MHW.zip
```

- Open the desired notebook by selecting **Open from Path** (Figure 45) in the menu and entering the name of the folder where the zip archive was unzipped, as specified in the table below (Table 5) and the notebook's name. E.g. for the MHW-Maps notebook write *MHW/MHW-Maps.ipynb* and for the MHW-Timeseries notebook write *MHW/MHW-Timeseries.ipynb*:

Figure 45. Open the desired notebook

Main path for compressed notebook archives in the workspace:

/workspace/VREFolders/MarineEnvironmentalIndicators/notebooks/

INDICATOR	Subpath in workspace	Archive name	Folder in JupyterLab	Notebook filenames
Ocean Heat Content (OHC)	OceanHeatContent	OHC.zip	OHC	OHC.ipynb
Trophic Index (TRIX)	EutropicathionIndicator	TRIX.zip	TRIX	TRIX.ipynb
Marine Heatwaves (MHW)	MarineHeatWaves	MHW.zip	MHW	MHW-Timeseries.ipynb, MHW-Maps.ipynb

Table 5. VLab 4 notebook archives in the workspace

The output produced by the notebooks is the user's personal workspace in: **/workspace/MEI**

6.3. Marine Heatwaves (MHWs)

This section is authored by Francesco Palermo, Giovanni Coppini, Emanuela Clementi, Ronan J. McAdam, Megi Hoxhaj, Rafael Gomes de Menezes, Fabrizio Antonio, Oussema Jerfel, Leandro Fernandes Patricio, Massimiliano Drudi, Antonio Mariani (CMCC).

6.3.1. State of art

Marine Heatwaves (MHWs) are prolonged periods of anomalously high sea surface temperatures (SSTs) that significantly impact marine ecosystems, biodiversity, and socio-economic activities.

Over recent decades, global ocean warming, particularly in the Mediterranean Sea, has led to increased intensity, frequency, and duration of these events. MHWs are defined as periods when SSTs exceed the 90th percentile of a baseline period for at least five consecutive days. This threshold-based approach considers both the duration and intensity of warming, making it a widely accepted standard for identifying MHWs (Hobday et al., 2016). The Mediterranean Sea is a hotspot for MHWs due to its semi-enclosed nature, high regional SST variability, and sensitivity to atmospheric and oceanic changes.

Figure 46. Comparison of summer SST anomalies during June - August of 2003 (top) and 2022 (bottom) MHWs in the Mediterranean Sea, relative to the corresponding 1993-2022 period.

The Mediterranean Sea has shown an accelerated warming trend, with SST increases ranging from 0.034 to 0.048 °C/year, surpassing the global average (Darmaraki et al., 2024). MHWs have been reported across various Mediterranean sub-basins, with notable events in 2003, 2012, 2017, and 2022. These events were characterized by SST anomalies exceeding 4°C and durations extending up to several months. For instance, the 2003 event affected 46-70% of the Mediterranean, with SST anomalies reaching up to 7°C, extensively studied for its ecological and economic impacts (Darmaraki et al., 2024 - Fig.43). In contrast, the 2022 MHW set records for its duration and geographic spread, covering up to 70% of the basin (McAdam et al. - Fig. 44).

Figure 47. Snapshots of SST anomalies and MHW occurrence during the different stages of the 2022 MHW. (a, c, e) - Reprocessed satellite observations. (b, d, f) - Forecasts with a lead time of 4 d.

The occurrence of MHWs results from complex interactions between atmospheric and oceanic processes. Key drivers include atmospheric forcing such as increased solar radiation, reduced cloud cover, and persistent anticyclonic conditions. Ocean dynamics also play a critical role, with reduced vertical mixing, strong stratification, and advection of warm water masses amplifying their effects. Additionally, large-scale climate modes such as the East Atlantic Pattern and North Atlantic Oscillation significantly modulate the characteristics of these events (Darmaraki et al., 2024).

MHWs have profound impacts on both ecological and socio-economic systems. Ecologically, they cause mass mortality of marine species, disrupt ecosystems, and drive shifts in species distributions (Darmaraki et al., 2024). Economically, they result in substantial losses for fisheries and aquaculture, while also affecting industries reliant on marine biodiversity. These impacts underscore the need for robust monitoring and forecasting systems. Recent advancements, such as the Copernicus Marine Service, have significantly enhanced our ability to detect and predict MHWs. Short-term forecasting systems, including the Mediterranean Forecasting System (MedFS), have demonstrated reliability in predicting the onset, intensity, and duration of these events, aiding in mitigation efforts (McAdam et al).

Despite significant progress, several challenges remain. Variations in MHW definitions and detection methodologies hinder cross-regional comparisons. Additionally, the limited understanding of subsurface MHWs and their vertical extent presents a research gap. Uncertainty in predicting long-term trends under

various emission scenarios and inadequate data on socio-economic impacts also complicate adaptive measures.

To address these gaps, future research should prioritize enhanced monitoring through the integration of satellite observations with in situ measurements. Developing coupled ocean-atmosphere models will better simulate MHW dynamics. Quantifying socio-economic impacts and identifying vulnerable regions will aid in crafting targeted mitigation strategies. Furthermore, leveraging scientific insights to inform climate adaptation policies will enhance resilience against these extreme events.

In conclusion, MHWs serve as a critical indicator of ocean health and the broader impacts of climate change. Advancements in detection, monitoring, and forecasting are essential to mitigate their adverse effects and ensure sustainable management of marine resources. The Mediterranean Sea, as a prominent MHW hotspot, offers valuable insights into the evolving dynamics of these phenomena and their far-reaching consequences.

6.3.2. Input data sources

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
Sea Surface Temperature (°C)	CMEMS Mediterranean Sea High Resolution and Ultra High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature Analysis https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00172	BlueCloud VRE, CMEMS
	CMEMS Mediterranean Sea - High Resolution L4 Sea Surface Temperature Reprocessed https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00173	
	CMEMS Mediterranean Sea Physics Analysis and Forecast https://doi.org/10.48670/mds-00359	

Table 6. VLab 4 MHW Input data sources

6.3.3. How to detect marine heatwaves dynamics

After following the steps described in Section 6.2, the user will find an MHW folder in JupyterLab containing two notebooks for operational **Marine Heatwaves (MHWs)** analysis over the Mediterranean Sea:

- `MHW-Timeseries.ipynb`: extraction and analysis of area-averaged Sea Surface Temperature (SST) time series to detect Marine Heatwave events.
- `MHW-Maps.ipynb`: computation of spatial maps of SST anomalies and MHW intensity for a selected date.

Both notebooks use Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) datasets (satellite L4 products and the Mediterranean Forecasting System — MFS) and rely on pre-computed climatologies.

How to use MHW-Timeseries notebook

1. Import required packages and **select the CMEMS dataset** from the available options (L4 REP, L4 NRT, or MFS):

Please select a Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) dataset:

Dataset:

2. **Climatology selection:** Choose the climatology reference file (e.g. 1987–2021 or 1993–2022) used to compute the daily climatological mean and the 90th percentile threshold.

Please select the Climatology file:

Climatology:

3. **Date range selection:** Select start and end dates using the date pickers. The notebook enforces minimum and maximum temporal windows and issues warnings for excessively large ranges.

Please select the date range:
Limits of the dataset -> from 2023-11-01 to 2026-01-17

Start:

End:

4. **Region selection:** choose either a predefined sub-region of the Mediterranean Sea:

Please select a boundary method (box or regions):

Method:

Select the Pre-defined region:

Region:

or custom rectangular domain defined by longitude and latitude bounds:

Please select a boundary method (box or regions):

Method: ▼

Insert the coordinates of the region of interest:
The standard values are the dataset limits.

Longitude:

Minimum:

Maximum:

Latitude:

Minimum:

Maximum:

5. **Processing:** the notebook applies area weighting, extracts the area-averaged SST time series, computes the daily climatology and percentiles for the selected period, and detects MHW events based on the configured thresholds and classification rules.
6. **Outputs and visualization:** interactive Plotly time series showing SST, climatology, 90th percentile threshold, and shaded MHW categories. Outputs include a standalone HTML figure and a NetCDF summary file. Figure 48 is the example result for the selected time period and region:

Figure 48. Example result for the selected time period and region

How to use MHW-Maps notebook

1. **Initial setup:** import required packages and **select the CMEMS dataset:**

Please select a Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) dataset:

Dataset:

2. **Data and climatology:** load the observed or model SST field for the selected date, together with the corresponding climatological mean and percentile fields:

Please select the Climatology file:

Climatology:

3. **Date selection:** specify the target date for the analysis:

Please select the date of interest:
 Dataset limits -> from 2008-01-13 to 2026-01-08

Date

4. **Region selection:** select a region of interest by specifying longitude and latitude bounds:

Insert the coordinates of the region of interest:
 The standard values are the dataset limits.

Longitude:

Minimum:

Maximum:

Latitude:

Minimum:

Maximum:

5. **Processing and visualization:** the notebook computes **SST anomalies** (SST minus climatology), standardized MHW intensity maps, and **MHW categories** at each grid point using the same thresholds adopted in the time series notebook. Outputs include PNG figures and NetCDF file. Figure 49 shows the example result for the selected time period:

Figure 49. Example result for the selected time period

Notes and recommendations

- A minimum recommended temporal window (default: 30 days) is enforced, as single-day diagnostics may be noisy; longer windows generally improve robustness.
- For forecast products (MFS), the notebook attempts to automatically detect the forecast start date and, when available, distinguishes forecast and analysis periods in the plots.
- Large temporal ranges or high-resolution spatial masks may significantly increase memory usage and execution time; users are advised to reduce the time span or select coarser regions for exploratory analyses.

6.4. Ocean Heat Content

This section is authored by Enrico Baglione, Paolo Oliveri and Simona Simoncelli (INGV).

6.4.1. State of art

The Ocean Heat Content (OHC) is considered an important Ocean Monitoring Indicator of ocean warming due to climate change. With about 90% of the excess heat accumulated in the Earth system deposited in

the world's ocean, the Earth Energy Imbalance causes rising ocean temperatures and increasing ocean heat content (OHC). Cheng et al. (2021; 2022; 2023; 2024) provide every year an updated estimate of OHC for the global ocean and its regional basins starting from the World Ocean Database data. Two different OHC products are used for the annual OHC report assessment (Fig. 47): (1) the Institute of Atmospheric Physics (IAP) at the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS); (2) National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI) at the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). The Mediterranean Sea is the ocean region that shows the highest warming (Fig. 36), thus it is extremely important to have a rapid and efficient OHC assessment. The Copernicus Marine Service also provides in its Ocean Monitoring Indicators catalogue the Mediterranean OHC Anomaly (0-700m) time series (Fig. 49) and trend from Reanalysis & Multi-Observations Reprocessing, but without a systematic yearly update.

The Blue Cloud 2026 proposal of OHC indicator would provide an operational workflow that would allow the rapid Mediterranean OHC estimation from multiple data sources. Moreover the use of the workbench 1 EOVS dataset, which will integrate data from the four main BDIs, would allow the maximization of data spatial and temporal coverage, reducing the associated product uncertainty.

OHC has been defined within the Copernicus Marine Service (von Schuckmann et al. 2016) as the deviation from a reference period and it is closely proportional to the average temperature change in a specific ocean layer, usually from the surface to 700 m or 2000m depth:

$$OHC = \rho_0 C_p \int_{z_1}^{z_2} (T_i - \underline{T}) dz$$

with a reference density (ρ_0) of 1030 kg m⁻³ and a specific heat capacity (C_p) of 3980 J/kg°C.

Within the SeaDataCloud project a Mediterranean OHC product was delivered (Simoncelli et al., 2020; 2021). Input data from SeaDataNet and CMS-CORA (version 5.2) were integrated and provided to DIVAnd tool to obtain temperature gridded fields (sliding decades) between the sea surface and 2000 m of depth, from which to compute OHC anomaly time series and trends in the layers 0-700 m (Fig. 50) and 0-2000 m. The workflow implemented in the framework of the SeaDataCloud project has been deployed in the MEI VLab and developments are ongoing to use the Beacon monolithic instances as input data, extending the time coverage closest to the present.

Figure 50. Global upper 2000m OHC from 1958 through 2023 according to (a) IAP/CAS and (b) NCEI/NOAA (1 ZJ = 1021 J). The line shows (a) monthly and (b) seasonal values, and the histogram presents (a) annual and (b) pentad anomalies relative to a 1981–2010 baseline. (Fig 2. from Cheng et al. 2024)

Figure 51. Regional observed upper 2000 m OHC change from 1958 through 2023 relative to a 1981-2010 baseline. (Fig 8. from Cheng et al. 2024)

Figure 52. Time series of annual mean area averaged ocean heat content in the Mediterranean Sea (basin wide), and integrated over the 0-700m depth layer during 1993-2019 (European Union-Copernicus Marine Service, 2019): ensemble mean and ensemble spread (shaded area). The ensemble mean is based on different data products, i.e. Mediterranean Sea Reanalysis, global ocean reanalysis GLORYS, C-GLORS, ORAS5, FOAM; global observational based products CORA, ARMOR3D.

Figure 53. Annual mean area averaged ocean heat content anomaly in the Mediterranean Sea (basin wide), and integrated over the 0-700m depth layer during 1960-2014 (Simoncelli et al. 2020; 2021).

6.4.2. Input data sources

The aim is to provide to the users an operational workflow to rapidly estimate the OHC indicator in the Mediterranean Sea from multiple historical datasets using the DIVAnd mapping tool for gridding temperature in situ data.

The evaluation of OHC indicator in the Mediterranean Sea domain will be possible from several input data sources listed in Table 7. The in situ temperature data spanning the time period after 1950 from CMEMS CORA, EuroArgo, World Ocean Database and SeaDataNet will be gathered querying the beacon monolithic instances available to the Blue-Cloud Vlabs. The data will then be an input to the DIVAnd tool for the generation of sliding decadal gridded fields to be used for the computation of the OHC from various data sources (Fig. 51). The present implementation of the OHC indicator uses temperature gridded fields computed by Simoncelli et al. (2020; 2021), but new temperature gridded fields from the above mentioned sources are in development. The OHC notebook will be updated accordingly. Moreover, once the Blue Cloud EOv dataset (WP3 output) will be produced, the relative OHC estimation will be integrated in the workflow.

The users can compute the OHC in sub-regions of the Mediterranean Sea, in different layers of the water column between the sea surface and 2000 m depth and for selected time periods.

Figure 54. Schematic representation of the OHC workflow.

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
In situ Temperature (°C)	CMEMS CORA	Data will be accessed using beacon monolithic instances to generate gridded Temperature fields with DIVAnd, from which to derive the OHC.
In situ Temperature (°C)	Argo	Data will be accessed using beacon monolithic instances to generate gridded Temperature fields with DIVAnd, from which to derive the OHC.
In situ Temperature (°C)	World Ocean Database	Data will be accessed using beacon monolithic instances to generate gridded Temperature fields with DIVAnd, from which to derive the OHC.
In situ Temperature (°C)	SeaDataNet	Data will be accessed using beacon

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
		monolithic instances to generate gridded Temperature fields with DIVAnd, from which to derive the OHC.
In situ Temperature (°C)	Blue Cloud EOV dataset (WP3 output)	Blue Cloud catalog

Table 7. VLab 4 OHC Input data sources

6.4.3. Step by step guideline to use the VLab

1. How to find The Jupyter Notebook

- 1) Once in <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/marineenvironmentalindicators> follow the instructions at paragraph 5.3 for installing the notebook (Figure 55).

Figure 55. Open the VLab

- 2) Access to the folder OHC (Figure 56).

Figure 56. Access the folder OHC

3) Inside the folder there is the OHC.ipynb notebook (Figure 57).

Figure 57. Open “OHC” folder

Now you can double click on the “OHC.ipynb” notebook and it will open in a new tab (Figure 58).

Figure 58. The notebook opened

2. How to work with the right Server Option

Be sure your Jupyterhub Server Option is settled on the Blue-Cloud Julia 1.9.3 - 8 Cores/32G RAM (Figure 59):

Figure 59. Blue-Cloud Julia 1.9.3 - 8 Cores/32G RAM

3. How to read and run the Jupyter Notebook

Be sure that the “Python[conda env:base]” kernel is correctly selected in the top-right panel of the jupyter notebook.

The notebook is divided into cells that can be executed sequentially, giving the possibility to the user to interact manually on some parameters.

The notebook serves for the OHC computation. The actual configuration:

- horizontal resolution = 0.125 degrees;
- The largest domain coinciding with a “Mediterranean” box: lon = [-5.625 36.5] degrees E, lat = [30 46] degrees N;
- Input 1955-2017 temperature sliding decades annual analysis from Simoncelli et al. (2020; 2021);
- Mask “gebco_2019_mask_1_8_edited_final.nc” edited opening and closing numerous zones and with removed less than 3 points connected components (WOA18 depth levels versions);
- OHC plots 0-2000m, computation and save in netCDF format for publication.

1. The Initial cells import the libraries and packages you need and define the Metadata to be correctly saved within the final results.
2. The “Data Reading” section defines the path to be followed to find/store the input/output data. These INPUT/OUTPUT folders are currently directed in the “blue-cloud-dataspace/MEI/INGV/” directory and in “/workspace/MEI/OceanHeatContent/”
3. The “Grid Selection” section defines some fixed parameters used for the calculation and the resolution of the gridded domain (Figure 60). It allows through the use of widgets the selection of latitude and longitude interval windows as like as the depth edges and the years window to which refer the following analysis. Executing the cells with the within-the-notebook panel , you load the domain and the time window selected.

Figure 60. Grid selection window

4. The following cells operate some mask instructions to select the desired domain and create the baseline for the temperature fields and the related plots.
5. In the “Load Temperature file” section the necessary temperature fields are loaded and some example plots of those loaded fields are shown over the selected domain (Figure 61), together with the Hov-Moeller plots for Temperature variable (Figure 62) and its anomaly for the time period (Figure 63).

Figure 61. Example plot of temperature

Figure 62. Example of Hoev-Moeller plot for temperature variable

Figure 63. Example plot for temperature anomaly

- The “Computation” section executes the OHC calculation for the loaded temperature fields over the selected domain, plotting the results within the Notebook, saving some plots in the OUTPUT directory and storing the numerical results, supplied by metadata, in a NetCDF file (Figure 64, 65 & 66).

```
plt.tight_layout()
# Save the plot as an image file with specified settings (e.g., resolution)
plt.savefig(OUTPUT_PATH+'TEMP_ANOMALY_TREND_'+suffix+'.png', bbox_inches='tight', dpi=200)

# Show the plot
plt.show()
```


Figure 64. Temperature anomaly output

```
plt.tight_layout()
# Save the plot as an image file with specified settings (e.g., resolution)
plt.savefig(OUTPUT_PATH+'OHC_700_ANOMALY_'+suffix+'.png', bbox_inches='tight', dpi=200)

# Show the plot
plt.show()
```


Figure 65. Ocean Heat Content anomaly output

Write output in netCDF dataset

```
[34]: # Handling netCDF file creation
out_file = OUTPUT_PATH+'Ocean_Heat_Content_WP4_'+suffix+'.nc'

# Delete the previous dataset if it exists
if os.path.isfile(out_file):
    os.remove(out_file)
    print(f"Removing file {out_file}")

# Create the output dataset
out_data = Dataset(out_file, "w", format="NETCDF4")

# Global attributes
out_data.setncatts({
    "Conventions": "CF-1.6"
})

# Define dimensions
depth_dim = out_data.createDimension("depth", 1)
time_dim = out_data.createDimension("time", len(years))
nv_dim = out_data.createDimension("nv", climatology_bounds.shape[0])

# Define variables
nctime = out_data.createVariable("time", "f8", ("time",))
nctime.units = "days since 1900-01-01 00:00:00"
nctime.standard_name = "time"
nctime.long_name = "time"
nctime.calendar = "standard"
nctime.climatology = "climatology_bounds"

ncdepth_bounds = out_data.createVariable("depth_bounds", "f8", ("nv", "depth"))
ncdepth_bounds.units = "m"

ncclimatology_bounds = out_data.createVariable("climatology_bounds", "f8", ("nv", "time"))
ncclimatology_bounds.units = "days since 1900-01-01 00:00:00"

# Variables for ocean heat content and temperature anomaly, using ("time", "depth") to switch dimensions
ncVariable1 = out_data.createVariable("Ocean_Heat_Content", "f4", ("time", "depth"), fill_value=9.96921e36, zlib=True)
ncVariable1.units = "J"
ncVariable1.standard_name = "ocean_heat_content"
ncVariable1.long_name = "Ocean Heat Content Anomaly"
ncVariable1.cell_methods = "time: mean within years time: mean over years"
```

Figure 66. NetCDF file output

All the output files (plots and netCDF) are saved with a suffix uniquely linked to the selection made by the user in the “Grid Selection” section.

6.4.4. Using other data sources

The proposed workflow is considering as input the data from the four main Blue Data Infrastructures and its added value will be the use of the Blue-Cloud EOv dataset produced within Workbench 1, which will integrate them. Since the OHC is the main climate change indicator, its estimation should be based on the maximum number of validated data. However the user might want to integrate its own additional temperature data in a target region for a customized estimate: the dataset should then be uploaded in the adopted NETcdf format and run the notebook changing the path of the input data.

6.5. Eutrophication Indicator: Trophic State Index, TRIX

This section is authored by [Nydia Catalina Reyes Suarez](#), [Marina Lipizer](#), [Oussema Fersi](#), [Nikola Holodkov](#), [Megan Anne French](#), [Alessandra Giorgetti](#) (OGS).

6.5.1 State of art

The assessment of the risks and impacts of eutrophication in estuarine and coastal waters is one of the key issues in marine environmental management (Painting, S.J., et al 2005). The Trophic index (TRIX), introduced by Volleinweider et al. (1998) to characterise the trophic conditions of seawater, is a linear combination of the logarithms of four state variables (Chl-a, DIN, TP and the absolute percentage deviation from oxygen saturation, aD%O). Therefore, this composite index aggregates pressure (nutrients), biological response (Chl-a, a proxy for biomass) and environmental disturbance in the water quality (oxygen) (Ærtebjerg, Gunni et al. 2001).

The trophic state depends on the availability of nitrogen and phosphorus for primary production, which in terms determines the phytoplankton biomass and oxygen saturation. In TRIX the nutrients are represented ideally by total nitrogen and total phosphorus; chlorophyll-a is a substitute parameter for phytoplankton biomass, as production is not routinely measured; and the deviation of oxygen saturation from 100% (aD%O) in the productive layer indicates the production intensity of the system (Ærtebjerg, Gunni et al. 2001). This simple index permits one to synthesise key eutrophication variables into a simple numeric expression to make information comparable over a wide range of trophic situations, while avoiding the subjectivity in the usage of traditional trophic terminology.

6.5.2. Input data sources

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
Water body Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN)	EMODnet Chemistry 2024 Eutrophication MediterraneanSea:	Data is not accessible via the Blue Cloud Data Access service. It has been uploaded to Vlab.
Water body chlorophyll-a (CHL)	- Eutrophication Med profiles 2024 unrestricted	The data is available through the bluecloud dataspace at: /blue-cloud-dataspace/MEI/Eutrophication_indicator/data/ The datasets are not yet public since the toolbox is still in beta testing.
Water body Total Phosphorus (TP)	- Eutrophication Med time series 2024 unrestricted	
Water body Dissolved Oxygen saturation (DO)	DIVAnd interpolated climatologies* calculated for the stated parameters (Chl-a, DIN, TP & DO%).	

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
	*The climatologies have been calculated by merging time series and profiles collections from EMODnet chemistry.	

Table 8. VLab 4 TRIX Input data sources

6.5.3. Identifying Eutrophication Hotspots with TRIX

You will work with the Jupyter Notebook TRIX.ipynb, which contains all the steps needed to calculate and visualize the TRIX eutrophication indicator. The workflow includes:

- 1) From the D4Science gateway <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/bluecloud-gateway> enter the **Marine environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab**. Once there choose JupyterHub (Figure 67).

Figure 67. Marine environmental Indicators VLab

- 2) In your Jupyterhub the following options will be granted (Figure 68).

Figure 68. Server options

- 3) Once the server has been chosen the user will be asked to pre-build the dash to create the interactive dashboard. Go on with *“build”* and *“save and reload”* (Figure 69).

Figure 69. Window to be selected to build the interactive dashboard

- 4) After following the instructions in paragraph 5.3 for unzipping the notebook, the user will now see some folders and a Jupyter Notebook in the column on the left of the screen. Select the *Jupyter Notebook TRIX.ipynb* (Figure 70).

Figure 70. Select the Jupyter Notebook TRIX.ipynb

The notebook contains all the necessary steps to:

a) Read the DIVAnd analysis outputs stored on the dataspace (Figure 71). DIVAnd climatologies have been calculated from in-situ data from EMODnet chemistry data collections for the Mediterranean sea representative of a time period of 10 years (2013-2023).

```
[3]: ds_DIN = xr.open_dataset(os.path.expanduser('~/.blue-cloud-dataspace/MEI/Eutrophication_indicator/new_data/Water_body_dissolved_inorganic_nitrogen_Med_merged03.4Dan1.nc'), decode_cf=True)
ds_CHL = xr.open_dataset(os.path.expanduser('~/.blue-cloud-dataspace/MEI/Eutrophication_indicator/new_data/Water_body_chlorophyll-a_Med_merged03.4Dan1.nc'), decode_cf=True)
ds_TP = xr.open_dataset(os.path.expanduser('~/.blue-cloud-dataspace/MEI/Eutrophication_indicator/new_data/Water_body_total_phosphorus_Med_merged03.4Dan1.nc'), decode_cf=True)
ds_DO = xr.open_dataset(os.path.expanduser('~/.blue-cloud-dataspace/MEI/Eutrophication_indicator/new_data/Water_body_dissolved_oxygen_saturation_Med_merged03.4Dan1.nc'), decode_cf=True)

[4]: # explore the dataset
ds_DO.to_dataframe().describe()
```

	climatology_bounds	dissolved_oxygen_saturation	dissolved_oxygen_saturation_L1	dissolved_oxygen_saturation_L2	dissolved_oxygen_saturation_rellr
count	4413864	1.627488e+06	269796.000000	427024.000000	1.627488e+06
mean	2007-12-31 03:00:00.000000	1.640905e+02	162.753723	162.675262	7.018350e-01
min	2003-01-01 00:00:00	1.499332e+01	14.993321	14.993321	0.000000e+00
25%	2003-06-08 06:00:00	1.565045e+02	154.861298	155.051575	4.763238e-01
50%	2007-12-31 00:00:00	1.624289e+02	160.100601	160.085297	8.455321e-01
75%	2012-07-23 00:00:00	1.690401e+02	167.644501	167.315643	9.692650e-01
max	2012-12-31 00:00:00	3.298778e+02	329.877808	329.877808	1.000000e+00
std	NaN	1.010859e+01	13.723577	13.040739	3.166726e-01

Figure 71. Read the DIVAnd analysis outputs stored on the dataspace

b) filter outliers using the ranges for the specific area (Figure 72).

Filtering out outliers:

This process ensures that only relevant data points are considered for each variable, based on predefined criteria for the North Adriatic Sea.

- **General Filtering Process:**
 - Values that fall outside the specified range are replaced with NaN (Not a Number), effectively filtering them out.
- **Variables and Ranges:**
 - **Chlorophyll_a (CHLF):**
 - Filters values to retain only those between 0 and 4.
 - **Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DINF):**
 - Filters values to retain only those between 0 and 30.
 - **Total Phosphorus (TPF):**
 - Filters values to retain only those between 0 and 1.
 - **Dissolved Oxygen Saturation (DOF):**
 - Filters values to retain only those between 0 and 120.

This filtering process is essential for focusing on the range of interest for each variable and discarding outliers or irrelevant data points.

```
[4]: CHLF = ds_CHL['chlorophyll-a'].where((ds_CHL['chlorophyll-a'] >=0) & (ds_CHL['chlorophyll-a'] <=4))
      DINF = ds_DIN['dissolved_inorganic_nitrogen'].where((ds_DIN['dissolved_inorganic_nitrogen'] >= 0) & (ds_DIN['dissolved_inorganic_nitrogen'] <=30))
      TPF = ds_TP.total_phosphorus.where((ds_TP.total_phosphorus >=0) & (ds_TP.total_phosphorus <=1))
      DOF = ds_DO['dissolved_oxygen_saturation'].where((ds_DO['dissolved_oxygen_saturation'] >= 0) & (ds_DO['dissolved_oxygen_saturation'] <=400))
```

Figure 72. Filter outliers using ranges for specific area

c) calculate the TRIX indicator by first checking the units and if necessary convert them (Figure 73). Absolute percentage deviation from oxygen saturation needs to be calculated in this step as well.

Each state variable is scaled by the highest (U_i) and the lowest (L_i) values in the data time series, and TRIX is defined as:

$$\text{TRIX} = \frac{k}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\log M_i - \log L_i)}{(\log U_i - \log L_i)}$$

where $k = 10$ is another scaling factor; $n = 4$ is the number of state variables considered; and M_i are the observed Chl, DO, DIN, and TP values.

Vollenweider et al. (1998) further simplified the TRIX formula by assuming (on the basis of the data used) that the difference ($\log U_i - \log L_i$) was equal to 3 for all state variables. Therefore, considering $k = 10$, $n = 4$, and the specific $\log L_i$ values, the TRIX formula was rewritten as follows:

$$\text{TRIX} = \frac{10}{12} [(\log M_{\text{Chl}} + 0.5) + (\log M_{\text{DO}} + 1) + (\log M_{\text{DIN}} - 0.5) + (\log M_{\text{TP}} + 0.5)]$$

Or

$$\text{TRIX} = \frac{1}{1.2} [(\log(M_{\text{Chl}} M_{\text{DO}} M_{\text{DIN}} M_{\text{TP}}) + 1.5)]$$

The latest equation gives the TRIX index currently used by ARPAE and adopted by the Italian national legislation (D.L 260/2010).

```
[15]: TRIX = abs((np.log10(CHL*DIN*TP*DO)+1.5)/1.2)
      print(np.nanmax(TRIX))
      print(np.nanmin(TRIX))
      6.0775857
      0.070939064
[27]: TRIX
[27]: xarray.DataArray (time: 12, depth: 12, lat: 234, lon: 251)
```

Figure 73. Calculate the TRIX indicator

The output TRIX is an array which contains spatial (lon, lat and depth) and temporal (monthly and seasonal) information which we will use to create the dashboard.

- 5) An interactive map is created from the output where the user can check the eutrophication state of an area of interest by changing depth and season (Figure 74).

Figure 74. Interactive map where the user can check the eutrophication state of an area of interest by changing depth and season.

6.5.4. Using other data sources

The VLab is currently running the beta version of the indicator for the Mediterranean Sea. By the end of the project in June 2026, an operational version of the indicator will be released. This final version will integrate EMODnet Chemistry and EOVI data available through the eutrophication workbench (WP3), covering European seas over two decades (the 2000s and 2010s). In parallel, the OTGA training module for the MEI VLab course will be available through the OTGA platform in February 2026. A revised version of the handbook will also be issued, incorporating detailed procedures and technical specifications for accessing the beta and operational implementation of the indicator.

In order to calculate the index with other data sources the user needs the following variables: Depth, water temperature, water body salinity, water body dissolved oxygen concentration, water body dissolved oxygen saturation, water body total phosphorus, water body chlorophyll-a and water body dissolved inorganic nitrogen. Then the following preprocessing steps should be applied:

1. Take the 0–100 m depth layer to consider only the eutrophication signal.
2. Take QFs 1, 2, 6, and Q for all parameters except depth and time (exclude QF 4).
3. The dissolved oxygen solubility concentration needs to be calculated for data compiling with application domain $T = 0–40\text{ °C}$ and $S = 0–40$ (Benson and Krause, 1984).

4. Calculate oxygen saturation from Benson and Krause, 1984.

Once this has been done, the code provides a way to discard outliers and to check units which is important for the final calculation of the TRIX index.

6.6. Storm Severity Index V2

This section is authored by Jan Willem Noteboom (KNMI) . The CCP execution section is authored by Marco Lettere, Vincenzo Cestone, Mauro Mugnaini (Nubisware S.r.l.).

6.6.1. State of the art

The Storm Severity Index (SSI) calculates maps and time series data to quantify exceptional atmospheric wind circumstances (i.e. storms) that indicate the risk of impact for the sea status and coastal regions. Individual storm events and storm seasons of areas can be calculated, classified and compared. In addition, the storm severity trend over longer periods of an area (30 years or more) can be calculated to investigate the storm climatology. SSI can be calculated for an area within the Northern Atlantic and European seas for a time period between 1940 and 2025 using time stepping (optional). To offer an SSI calculation that can handle large datasets for the Northern Atlantic and European seas over 85 years, a relatively quick and easy method has been chosen where SSI is solely based on wind speed (1).

$$SSI_{k,day} = \sum_{t=1}^{T=24h} [(max(0, \frac{v_{k,t}}{v_{Prec,k}} - 1)^3] * A_k \quad (1)$$

$SSI_{t,k}$ represents the calculated index for time period T and area K

t represents a timestep within time period T

k represents a grid cell within area K

$v_{t,k}$ represents the wind speed at timestep t , grid cell k

$v_{Prec,k}$ represents the percentile value (90th, 95th, 98th or 99th) of the max. wind speed at grid cell k .

A_k represents the area of grid cell k divided by a reference cell at the equator (correction for distance per degree).

To calculate the impact perspective of wind, SSI uses the presence of *exceptional wind power*. *Wind power* is defined as the dynamic wind pressure (kinetic energy) multiplied by the run of wind. Hence wind power is proportional to the cubic wind speed (v^3). *Exceptional* is defined by the exceedance of the (hourly) wind speed percentile for a reference period. The P90, P95 , P98 and P99 wind speed percentiles of a grid cell

represent the lower limit of the highest 10%, 5%, 2% or 1% wind speed values. A climate standard normal period (30 years) can be selected as the reference period.

The calculated SSI maps and time series data are stored in a NetCDF file. In addition, plots of maps and time series can be created and stored in separate files.

6.6.2. Input data sources

Variables	Data Sources	Data Access
Hourly wind speed, $v_{t,k}$	C3S ERA5 (hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present) Downloaded as time consecutive wind speed data files (NetCDF) -no time gaps, same area- Time period: 1940 – 2025 Area: Northern Atlantic and European seas (latitude 30.0 to 73.0, longitude -60.0 to 48.0)	Blue-cloud-dataspace StormSeverityIndicator/SSI_v2/input
Hourly wind speed percentiles P_{90}, P_{95}, P_{98} and $P_{99}, v_{Prec,k}$	Wind speed percentile data files for 6 time reference periods (NetCDF) Created from downloaded ERA5 wind speed data files using scripts.	Blue-cloud-dataspace StormSeverityIndicator/SSI_v2/pvalues <u>Scripts & data to create pvalues :</u> StormSeverityIndicator/SSI_v2/pvalues /pvalues_file_generation

Table 9. Storm severity index - data sources

The notebook requires consecutive NetCDF data files with hourly wind speed data. These data files have been downloaded from the Copernicus C3S Climate Data Store (CDS) using dataset *ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present* where parameter *Ocean surface stress equivalent 10m neutral wind speed* has been selected for the Northern Atlantic and Europe Sea area (latitude 30.0 to 73.0, longitude -60.0 to 48.0, 0.5x0.5 degree grid) and consecutive times periods between 1 January 1940 and 16 November 2025.

Note: new data files (after 16 November 2025) can be added but should be time consecutive, covering the same area and not include chunking (that is automatically applied when downloading data from C3S). The following command should be used to remove the chunking
`$nccopy -c wind:1,87,217 file_chk.nc file_no_chk.nc`

The NetCDF data files with calculated windspeed percentile values P90, P95, P98 and P99 cover a period of 30 years for the Northern Atlantic and Europe seas area grid. There are 6 different 30 year periods

available: 1940-1969; 1950-1979, 1960-1989, 1970-1999, 1980-2010, 1990-2019. These reference periods represent Climatological standard normal periods.

6.6.3 How to perform a Storm Severity Index calculation notebook

This section includes step by step guidelines for SSIv2 calculation by the notebook implementation and the CCP implementation.

6.6.3.1. How to install, run and configure SSIv2 notebook

This section will guide you through the installation, running and configuration of SSI calculations using the **SSiv2 notebook**. In addition, some calculation examples are demonstrated.

How to install SSI version 2 notebook

After registration and sign in of the Blue-Cloud environment (blue-cloud.d4science.org) go to the *MarineEnvironmentalIndicators* (top-right menu). On the Marine Environmental Indicators page, start *JupyterLab* (menu) and use the default machine. After JupyterLab has started, launch a *Terminal* and enter the following commands:

```
jovyan@jupyter-janwillem-2enoteboom:~$ cd
jovyan@jupyter-janwillem-2enoteboom:~$ pwd
/home/jovyan
jovyan@jupyter-janwillem-2enoteboom:~$ cp ~/workspace/VREFolders/MarineEnvironmentalIndicators/notebooks/StormSeverityIndicator/StormSeverityIndicator_v2.zip .
jovyan@jupyter-janwillem-2enoteboom:~$ unzip StormSeverityIndicator_v2.zip
Archive:  StormSeverityIndicator_v2.zip
  creating:  StormSeverityIndicator_v2/
  creating:  StormSeverityIndicator_v2/output/
  inflating: StormSeverityIndicator_v2/SSI_v2.ipynb
  inflating: StormSeverityIndicator_v2/README.txt
jovyan@jupyter-janwillem-2enoteboom:~$ cd StormSeverityIndicator_v2
jovyan@jupyter-janwillem-2enoteboom:~/StormSeverityIndicator_v2$ ls
output  README.txt  SSI_v2.ipynb
jovyan@jupyter-janwillem-2enoteboom:~/StormSeverityIndicator_v2$
```

Figure 75. Installation instructions for notebook SSIv2

Now open the SSI v2 notebook: *SSI_v2.ipynb*

Figure 76. Notebook SSIv2 in JupyterLab

How to run the notebook

After you open the notebook, you can run the entire notebook to check if the notebook is properly installed. You can press the following button (and press OK on Restart Kernel):

Please wait 2-3 minutes for completion (i.e. no more red CPU activity).

How to configure SSI parameters

After completion, scroll down the notebook. After *SSI input*, the time and area coverage of the input or source data is presented.

Scroll further down to SSI calculation parameters.

SSI calculation parameters

Next, input widgets are presented to specify the SSI calculation parameters.

Note: after you have specified the calculation parameters using widgets, please make sure that you **move to and executed the**

- ▶ Name SSI calculation
- ▶ Time period
- ▶ Time stepping
- ▶ Area Size
- ▶ Climate Normal
- ▶ Threshold (wind speed)

*** NOTE: Please MOVE to the NEXT CELL and RUN CELL (<shift><enter>) to activate your input setting ***

You can now unfold these parameters.

▼ Name SSI calculation

Name of SSI calculation (used by calculation output file and plotting files)

SSI calc:

▼ Time period

Select a time period between 1940-01-01 and 2025-11-16

Start date:

▼ Time stepping

Enable timestepping and select a timestep unit and size

Time stepping:

Step unit:

If you choose to perform **Time stepping** (check box) with the Time period, you can select the size of the time step in *Days, Months* or *Years*. Only a *Step size* of 1 to 10 is available.

▼ Area Size

Select a bounding box: latitude 30.0 till 73.0 and longitude -60.0 till 48.0

Lat(deg):

35.0 – 62.0

Long(deg): -20.0 – 35.0

▼ Climate Normal

Select a climate normal (30 years period) as reference for the threshold data

Cli. normal: ▼

There are 6 different reference datasets or climate normal periods available. The selected dataset is used to collect the wind speed percentile data.

▼ Threshold (wind speed)

Select as threshold a percentile P90, P95, P98 or P99 (with min. value), or a fixed value

Select:

- Percentile
- Percentile with min.
- Fixed

Percentile:

- P90
- P95
- P98
- P99

Fixed threshold value (or min. perc value) in m

This threshold or exceptional wind speed level data is by default Percentile P98 limited by a min percentile value of 15 m/s. Alternatively, other Percentiles and minimum values can be selected but also a Fixed wind speed value for all grid cells can be used as threshold data.

Next, a summary of all the calculation parameters is given.

```

Validate and summarize the SSI calculation input
Next, the SSI calculation input are validated and summarized.

...

Output filename: output/SSIcalc1.nc
Pvalues filename: /home/jovyan/blue-cloud-dataspace/StormSeverityIndicator/SSI_v2/pvalues/C3S_ERA5_North_Atlantic_EU_1990-2019_ocean_wind_speed_Pvalues.nc
SUMMARY OF SSI CALCULATION INPUT:
Start: 2013-01
End(not included): 2015-01
Stepsize: 1 Months
Number of steps = 24
Latitude range: 35.0 62.0
Longitude range: -20.0 35.0
Windspeed threshold percentile P98 with minimum value 15.0
    
```

Figure 77. Summary of calculation parameters for notebook SSIv2

Now the actual calculation starts and a progress bar is displayed.

```

Start SSI calculations
Next, the SSI map or grid data and time series data for the area are calculated.
A progressbar is displayed.

...

Calculating: 
    
```

This calculation is performed three phases:

- (1) First, hourly SSI values are summed up to daily SSI values.
- (2) Second, all days within a time step are summated.
- (3) Third, the area of a time step is calculated by summing up the SSI of the included grid cells.

$$SSI_{k,day} = \sum_{t=1}^{T=24h} [(max(0, \frac{v_{k,t}}{v_{prec,k}} - 1)^3] * A_k \quad (1) \quad SSI_{k,step} = \sum_{t=1}^{Stepsize} SSI_{k,day} \quad (2)$$

$$SSI_{step,area} = \sum_{k=1}^{Areasize} SSI_{k,step} \quad (3)$$

In addition to the time step SSI(total), the SSI_{max}, SSI_{rate} and SSI_{day} are calculated for each grid cell as well as the entire selected area.

- SSI(total), the total cumulative SSI value (all days in a timestep)
- SSI_{max}, the maximum SSI day value
- SSI_{rate}, the average SSI day value (zero values excluded)
- SSI_{day}, number of days the SSI day value is greater than zero

The calculated time step SSI grid cell data and SSI area data are stored in a NetCDF file.

▼ Save calculated SSI map or grid data and timeseries data in the output file

Next, the calculated SSI data are saved in the specified output file (NetCDF) in the output directory

...

STORAGE OF CALCULATED SSI DATA
 SSI grid data (steps, cells latitude, cells longitude : (24, 54, 110)) and time series data saved to file output/SSICALC1

Using the SSI calculated maps and times series data, plots can be selected and created.

SSI plots (maps and time series)

Next, input widgets are presented to select the maps and time series for plotting that saved in files (png) in the output directory.

Note1: the number of map plots is limited to 25 by default. This limit can be updated and set to 0 for unlimited plots

Note2: after you have specified your plots using the widgets, please make sure that you **move to and execute the next cell** to read the plotting input

...

📄 ↑ ↓ 🔍 🗑️

▶ Select SSI variables

▶ Select plot types

▶ Set plotting limit

*** NOTE: Please MOVE to an EXECUTE NEXT CELL to read your plotting setting ***

Unfolding these plotting parameters will present:

▼ Select SSI variables

SSI_{total}
 SSI_{max}
 SSI_ndays
 SSI_{rate}

▼ Select plot types

Create map plots
 Create time series plots

▼ Set plotting limit

Select the maximum number of plots (0 till 100)

Limit:

Finally, using these plotting parameters, plots are created and stored in *png files* in the output directory together with the NetCDF (.nc) file.

Figure 78. SSIv2 output data and plots

Examples of SSI calculation

- Storms in NW Europe

Figure 79. SSI maps of storms in North West Europe

- Medicanes

Figure 80. SSI maps of Medicanes

- Storm seasons

Figure 81. SSI maps and time series of storm seasons

- Storm climatology 1940 - 2025

Figure 82. SSI maps and time series of storm climatology

6.6.3.2 How to execute SSI on the Cloud Computing Platform

The Storm Severity Index v2 (SSIV2) has been ported to the new Blue-Cloud VRE Analytics Engine: the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP). CCP, runs within D4Science, which provides the VRE enabling technology

underpinning Blue Cloud. By using CCP, scientists can publish their methods and algorithms, making them accessible for users to run in accordance with FAIR principles.

Compared to the Jupyter Notebook–based implementation, the CCP version introduces several key differences:

- **No reliance on local data:** Instead of requiring downloaded datasets, it can directly subset the necessary wind data from multiple providers of the ERA5 hourly dataset (Copernicus Climate Data Store and Destination Earth Data Hub).
- **Efficient data reuse:** It can selectively reuse data generated in previous runs, saving both time and computational resources during remote subsetting.
- **Global coverage:** Unlike region-specific implementations, it is not restricted to particular geographic areas and covers the entire globe.
- **Flexible climatology normals:** Normals are not limited to fixed year ranges but can span any 30-year period.
- **Interactive visualization:** In addition to static map images, it produces an interactive dashboard powered by Plotly.

This section demonstrates how to use SSIv2 on CCP by tracking two Mediterranean Hurricanes (Medicanes):

- **Qendresa**, which struck the Mediterranean region near Tunisia, Malta, and Sicily in November 2014.
- **Zorbas**, which developed across the Ionian and Aegean Seas in September 2018.

To access CCP through its dedicated interfaces, users can enter the **Marine Environmental Indicator VLab** and select the **Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)** option available under the main **Analytics Engine** menu.

For those interested in exploring CCP in greater depth, a link to a comprehensive documentation resource is also available.

Figure 83. Where to find access to CCP

On the **CCP method execution page**, a list of available methods is displayed on the left-hand side. All methods shared within the VLab are visible here and organized into their respective categories.

Users can locate methods either by browsing through the list or by using the search field to enter part of the method’s name, description, tags, or category.

Figure 84. Find Storm Severity Index v2 by searching

By clicking the green play icon or by drag and dropping the method onto the **Method Execution** form the user can prepare for executing the SSiv2.

Figure 85. Prepare for execution on the Method Execution form

To configure the execution for tracking Qendresa, the user has to set the parameters according to the following table and use the geographic tool (small world icon) to export a WKT polygon encompassing the Mediterranean Sea.

Input	Value	Description
Annotation for execution	2014_Qendresa	A label to better identify the execution
Data source	edh	The data source provider from where to subset input data which is hourly wind speed at 10m height. edh is EarthDataHub which is very fast compared to the other alternative (copernicus) which accesses data on Copernicus Climate Data Store. d4science can be used if the input data is already stored on the D4Science workspace.

Geography	A WKT	Use the associated geo widget to export a WKT polygon encompassing the Mediterranean sea (as shown in following Figure). This will limit the geographic subset for the input data and possibly climate normals computation.
Start date	Nov 7th, 2014	First day of analysis. This is the lower limit of the input data time subset.
End date	Nov. 9th, 2014	Last day of analysis. This is the upper limit of the input data time subset.
Resample count	3	Count of time stepping period. Using the full extent of the time subset no time stepping is actually performed.
Resample period	D	Resample period: D is for days.
Threshold type	both	Use both fixed threshold and percentile for cutting lower amounts from the input data.
Threshold	15	The fixed lower threshold for wind speed cutoff values to consider in computation.
Variables to plot	SSItotal	Generate images only for the SSItotal variable
Variables for interactive dashboard	SSItotal, SSIAreatotal, wind	Populate an interactive dashboard with these variables including original wind data.
Data source for climate normals data	edh	Select Earthdatahub source for climate normals data
Climate normals reference date	12-31-2019	Choose 1990-2019 as thirty years period for climate normals

percentile	98	Choose 98th percentile for wind speed cutoff to consider in computation.
Data url		Leave blank because we are not reusing any data already stored in the workspace.
D4Science url for reusing climate normals data		Leave blank because we are not reusing any cached climate normals data.
Options	Automatically archive whole execution provenance	After computation, synchronise everything to the user's workspace.

Table 10. Parameter setting for Qendresa.

Figure 86. Select the Mediterranean area with the Geographic input tool

When all the required inputs have been set correctly the **Execute button** will be activated and by clicking it, a new execution of SSIv2 will start.

The execution shows up on the **Execution Monitor** widget with all the according status changes and logs updating in near real time.

CCP system logs are shown in white, the execution's Standard Output (stdout) and Standard Error (stderr) channels are shown in green and red respectively.

Figure 87. Execution Monitor widget showing progress of SSIv2.

Once the execution successfully completes the corresponding Execution Monitor entry is populated with links to all the related metadata and outputs.

Every resource can be opened directly in the browser (if MIME type is supported) or downloaded by clicking on the proper links and icons.

The url can also be copied to the clipboard.

Figure 88. All the links to metadata and outputs related to execution are shown after completion.

By clicking for example on the link of the output named **dashboard.html** a new browser tab is opened and the result of the computation performed during the execution is plotted in an interactive HTML dashboard.

The dashboard contains plots for all the variables that have been selected before starting the execution.

Figure 89. The Qendresa storm depicted in the interactive dashboard.

Next step we want to run a similar analysis in order to track the Zorbas 2018 Medcane and the following table reports the parameters to set for this new case.

Input	Value	Description
Annotation for execution	2018_Zorbas	A label to better identify the execution
Data source	edh	Same as before
Geography	A WKT	Same as before
Start date	Sep 26th, 2018	First day of analysis. This is the lower limit of the input data time subset.
End date	Sep 30th, 2018	Last day of analysis. This is the upper limit of the input data time subset.

Resample count	1	This time we consider 1 day of resampling so that plotting snapshots are produced for every day of the period generating an animated dashboard.
Resample period	D	Resample period: D is for days.
Threshold type	both	Same as before
Threshold	15	Same as before
Variables to plot	SSItotal	Same as before
Variables for interactive dashboard	SSItotal, SSIareatotal, wind	Same as before
Data source for climate normals data	edh	Same as before but this time it will be ignored.
Climate normals reference date	12-31-2019	Same as before but this time it will be ignored.
percentile	98	Same as before but this time it will be ignored.
Data url		Leave blank because we are not reusing any data already stored in the workspace.
D4Science url for reusing climate normals data	URL to previous climate_normals.nc	Reuse the previously computed normals climate_normals.nc as described below.
Options	Do not archive anything automatically	This time we do not want to save everything to the workspace. It can also be done manually after execution.

Table 11. Parameter setting for Zorbas.

As described in the table for the parameters, this time, we want to reuse the previous execution which did the heavy lifting of computing the 98th percentile from fetched wind data for the 30 years period 1990-2019. This optimization will save a significant amount of time during the execution.

This can be done in two ways:

- By browsing, at the corresponding input widget (with the blueish folder icon), to the workspace location where the previous execution has been archived. Then export the protected link of the resource stored under **outputs/climate_normals.nc** which will populate the input parameter accordingly (Figure 90).
- By using the **copy link** functionality in the Execution Monitor widget on the climate_normals.nc resource reported among the outputs and paste it into the according input of the Execution form (Figure 91).

Figure 90. Browsing to the archived execution

Figure 91. Copying the link directly from the Execution Monitor

Once all the parameters have been set, by clicking on the Execute button, the execution starts and after a significantly shorter time it completes producing an output that tracks Zorbas 2018.

This time the dashboard contains an animation of three frames, one per day of resampling and also time series data for area total variables.

Figure 92. The interactive, animated dashboard tracking the Zorbas 2018 storm.

6.6.4. Using other data sources

This SSI calculation method needs hourly wind speed data above sea with a spatial resolution of 0.5 x 0.5 degrees. The notebook is now limited to the Northern Atlantic and European seas since 1940. Other data sources downloaded from the C3S ERA5 can be used that cover a different (larger) area and time period. There are scripts available to pre-calculate the required percentile data for the notebook.

However, the CCP implementation of SSI is already capable of handling SSI calculations for areas worldwide since 1940 (i.e. the time and spatial coverage of ERA5 data source).

Other data sources, outside ERA5, can be used but require data transformation to the ERA5 data format in NetCDF (see ERA5 for details). For data sources with a different (higher) spatial resolution the calculation method needs to be modified.

6.7. The Marine Environment Indicators (MEI) Webapp service

The **Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI)** service is a web graphical interface that enables users to monitor and evaluate the environmental conditions of marine areas, providing essential support for decision-making in ocean management. By integrating multiple data sources, the platform offers a unified data analysis service, facilitating online computation of indicators. The output is available as either a time series or a map.

Generating value-added data involves a straightforward process where users define specific parameters and the system handles the complex data extraction and transformation. The entire workflow is managed through an intuitive interface that communicates with the [Cloud Computing Platform \(CCP\) service](#) of VLab4 for computing the desired outputs.

The flexibility of the service allows users to specify the desired output type, which depends on the indicator chosen, among:

Method's name (Indicator)	Output type
Marine Heatwaves	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MHW and Temperature Anomalies Map ● MHW Categories Map ● MHW Timeseries
Ocean Heat Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Temperature anomaly timeseries ● OHC Anomaly Timeseries
Storm Severity Index 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Percentile ● Percentile & Fixed ● Fixed

Table 12. Output types per indicator

According to the selected output type and field, additional parameters (proposed by the MEI) are required for the finalization of a processing request.

The MEI Generator service offers to the user an easy and transparent way to process data from external data sources and the interface presents to the user all the possible options, which are needed for the customization of the processing.

The MEI Generator service offers users an easy and transparent way to process data from external data sources. The interface presents all possible options needed for customizing the processing.

The functionalities currently provided are summarized as follow:

- Generating new output starting from available data
- Access and visualize previously calculated data

The process of output generation consists of four key steps: parameter configuration, job submission, progress monitoring, and result retrieval. Once submitted, the user's request is queued for processing, and they can track its status in real-time until completion.

Generating new output starting from available data

To generate value-added data, please follow the instructions:

1. Open MEI Generator app from the VRE menu
2. Select the desired output, by providing the following information
 - a. the desired **method** (*Figure 93a*) - i.e. *Ocean Heat Content*
 - b. the **output type** (*Figure 93b*) - i.e. *Temperature anomaly timeseries*
 - c. the desired **data source** (*Figure 93c*) - i.e. *Temperature_sliding_climatology_WP*
3. Select the additional input parameters :
 - a. the **time range** (*Figure 93d*)
 - b. the **area** of interest in terms of boundaries (*Figure 93e*)
 - c. the **depth** layer if available (*Figure 93f*)
4. Click on the “Execute process” button (*Figure 93g*)

After configuration, the processing request for a new output is submitted to the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) service for calculation.

Figure 93. Generate new outputs

Drag & Drop Area Corners

The points of minimum latitude and longitude and the points of maximum latitude and longitude define the area of interest. The chosen area (blue rectangle on the map) is visible on the map that is centered on the geographic domain of the selected data source.

Use drag and drop on the interactive map to define your area corners. Click on the marker to show/hide the possible area.

Area permissions

The map shows permitted and restricted areas using color coding:

- **Green areas:** Permitted for data extraction
- **Red areas:** Restricted or unavailable data
- **Blue areas:** Area selected

Access and visualize previously calculated data

By selecting the **My requests** tab (Figure 93h), users can see the status of recently launched processes and, after completion, access the output. The information shown in the table (Figure 94) includes:

- the chosen method;
- the creation time for each process;
- the current status of their execution and access to outputs (Figure 94b);
- the data source;
- the output type;
- the output field;
- the area of interest;
- the depth range;
- the time range;

Generate new outputs			My requests				Help		
Method	Creation time	Status	^a Outputs	Data source	Output Type	Output Field	Area [lon,lat]	Depth [m]	Time range
Ocean Heat Content	2025-12-30 16:06:10	successful	^b Show	Temperature_sliding_climatology_WP	Temperature anomaly timeseries	Sea Surface Temperature	[-4.99, 34] [10.2, 44.82]	N/A	1960 to 2014
Storm Severity Index 2	2025-12-30 16:05:50	successful	Show	C3S_ERA5_ME DSEA	Fixed	N/A	[-4.99, 34] [10.2, 44.82]	N/A	1940
Storm Severity Index 2	2025-12-30 16:05:42	successful	Show	C3S_ERA5_ME DSEA	Percentile & Fixed	N/A	[-4.99, 34] [10.2, 44.82]	N/A	1940
Marine Heat Waves	2025-12-30 16:05:29	successful	Show	SST_MED_SST_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_010_021	MHW Timeseries	Sea Surface Temperature	[-4.99, 34] [10.2, 44.82]	N/A	2020-05-03 to 2020-09-03
Marine Heat Waves	2025-12-30 16:02:26	failed	^c Request metadata	MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013	MHW Timeseries	Sea Surface Temperature	[-4.99, 34] [10.2, 44.82]	N/A	2025-05-03 to 2025-09-03

^d [Previous](#) [1](#) [2](#) [Next](#)

Figure 94. My requests

It is possible to order the rows by clicking on each column header, and at the bottom of the table (Figure 94d), users can navigate through pages using pagination.

When the status of the process is presented as “successful”, users can visualize the data produced by the process by clicking on the “Show” button (Figure 94b).

In case of failure execution logs (stdout/stderr) will be available for debugging and tracking (Figure 94c).

Results and Downloads

Users can access the results screen (Figure 48) where they can:

- Download the image (Figure 95a)
- Download the NetCDF file (Figure 95b)
- Download the execution log (Figure 95b)

Figure 95. Example outputs from Marine Heatwaves

Figure 96. Example outputs from Ocean Heat Content

Figure 97. Example outputs from Storm Severity Index v2

Help Page

A help page is also available for additional guidance clicking on the header tab (Figure 93i).

7. Introduction to VLab 5 “Global Fisheries Atlas”

This section is authored by Julien Barde, Bastien Grasset (IRD), Yannis Marketakis (FORTH) and FAO and tuna RFMOs data managers from FIRMS (IOTC, ICCAT, IATTC, WCPFC, CCSBT).

The Global Fisheries Atlas VLab acts as an umbrella built on top of authoritative data or knowledge sources describing fisheries activities (Table 13).

This VLab aims to better describe fisheries activities at a global scale either by disseminating knowledge or data. To do so, more than ten sources have been harmonised and are accessible from the Global Fisheries Atlas. The VLab content is made accessible by various entry points either through **graphic user interface (GUI)** or programmatic access depending on users needs and profiles. Users can access or use web mapping products to browse and explore the **Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)** knowledge base as well as datasets describing Tuna Atlas fisheries at a global scale. Beyond data already integrated, this VLab also provides methods and tools to reproduce, update or customize this work to deal with other use cases. It is worth mentioning here some documents describing the first versions of Global (Tuna) Fisheries Atlas delivered first by FAO and IRD : see bibliography <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/collection/firms-tuna-atlas> .

For what regards **GRSF**:

- Programmatic access
 - GRSF API
 - GRSF SPARQL endpoint
- GUIs
 - GRSF CKAN catalogue and map viewer (Figure 100)

For what regards **Global Tuna Atlas**:

- Programmatic access
 - Zenodo GUIs and API to access the main versions of data or code releases
 - R code in RStudio projects
- GUIs
 - Zenodo DOIs for both data and code
 - Shiny apps
 - Dynamic reports: R markdown

7.1. Target Users & Community

Among possible users of the data products and code made available by the Global Fisheries Atlas VLab, we identified the following profiles:

- **Scientists**
 - Fisheries Scientists
 - Updating the current time series of catch and fishing effort remains the main goal of the Global Tuna Atlas. This task is meant to be achieved by the early adopters of the VLab consolidated group (**Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System (FIRMS)** members: scientists and **Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs)** data managers). Indeed, this work is already used and advertised by the FIRMS network (**Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO)** and RFMOs), datasets have also been assigned DOIs on Zenodo.
 - Accessing updated time series of catch and fishing effort data to e.g. calibrate models, drive stock assessment and population dynamics models.
 - Understand, reproduce or customize the work to tailor new Global Fisheries Atlas for other species (e.g. by executing the work from the VLab RStudio server).
 - Marine Biologists
 - Finding data describing species distribution and abundance that are essential biological variables for ecological research and ocean observatories also called **Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)**.
 - Climate Change Analysts
 - To study the impact of climate on fisheries by running cross domain analysis with physical and chemical parameters (e.g. ocean temperature data, salinity levels, and other climate-related factors).
 - Data scientists can use available fisheries data e.g. to train **AI** models and cross-domain analysis with environmental parameters such as those provided by Copernicus.
- **Policy Makers, Commercial Fisheries, and Conservation Organizations**
 - Conservation Organizations and NGOs
 - Will benefit from detailed fisheries data for habitat protection efforts, biodiversity conservation strategies, and environmental impact assessments.
 - Policy Makers and Regulatory Bodies

- RFMOs and other policymakers can utilize the GFA for helping craft legislation and marine spatial planning
- Commercial Fisheries and Industry Stakeholders
 - Operators, fisheries managers, and industry representatives can leverage the GFA for strategic planning, sustainable practice adoption.
- **Data managers in the marine domain and beyond** : interested in implementing similar data management plans for other kinds of data can reuse (execute and customize) the code directly in the VLab. Developers will find “ready to go” solutions for the FAIR management of fisheries data (e.g. time-series on catch and effort that brings collated statistical data into a data harmonization and QC process with dynamic R markdown reports).
- **End-users**: general public with an interest in stocks and fisheries, fish provenance, fisheries distribution, fisheries and SDG2 and SDG 14, are meant to access VLab products through e.g. web-portals, atlases, API's or QR codes.

7.2. State of art

High-resolution data in the fisheries domain (meaning at the fishing operation level) are often highly confidential, primarily due to economic and strategic interests. However, there is an increasing demand from both scientists and the public for fisheries data, information, and knowledge to be made accessible in order to address emerging scientific questions and support informed decision-making. Despite this, there is currently no global policy or EU directive enforcing the FAIR principles for fisheries data, nor is there a standardized fisheries data management framework comparable to the e.g. INSPIRE or Water framework directives, which mandate the FAIRness of spatial data by implementing OGC standards.

As a result, we used pre-harmonized public domain datasets that are reported by countries to the RFMOs at a lower spatio-temporal resolution (e.g. using grids at a 1° or 5° per month). These datasets are made freely available on RFMOs Websites but have not been assigned DOIs and unfortunately don't share the same structure. Indeed, unlike other domains, the fisheries sector lacks widely adopted *de facto* or international *standards* for data formats, which underscores the need for our VLab to harmonize the heterogeneous data structures provided by RFMOs. This is the reason why we promote the implementation of the CWP standards for fisheries domain data and the reason why we have to focus on specific use cases like tuna fisheries as we can't harmonize all fisheries datasets worldwide in the framework of a single project.

7.3. Input data sources

This VLab uses four different sources to build the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) knowledge base and some of the public domain datasets provided by the five tuna Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs). The main characteristics of the data sources are described in the table below.

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
GRSF	RAM legacy database	GRSF Knowledge Base
GRSF	FAO SDG 14.4.1 Questionnaire	GRSF Knowledge Base
GRSF	Fishsource	GRSF Knowledge Base
GRSF	FIRMS	GRSF Knowledge Base
Catch and effort	IOTC	Global Tuna Atlas: Zenodo
Catch and effort	ICCAT	Global Tuna Atlas: Zenodo
Catch and effort	IATTC	Global Tuna Atlas: Zenodo
Catch and effort	<u>WCPFC</u> Last data updated up to 2023: https://www.wcpfc.int/doc/annual-catch-estimates-2022-data-files	Global Tuna Atlas: Zenodo
Catch and effort	<u>CCSBT- Southern bluefin tuna (SBF)</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● annual catch data by year, flag <u>or</u> gear covering 1952-2023: https://www.ccsbt.org/userfiles/file/data/GlobalCatch_Flag_Gear.xlsx ● annual catch data by year, flag, <u>and</u> ocean covering 1965-2023: https://www.ccsbt.org/userfiles/file/data/CatchByOYF.xlsx 	Global Tuna Atlas: Zenodo

VARIABLES	DATA SOURCES	DATA ACCESS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● However, for the GTA, we do need the annual catch data by <u>year, flag, gear, and ocean</u> covering 1952-2023 which was directly sent by the CCSBT colleague (dataset covering 1965-2021) last year ● geo-referenced catch and effort data for fisheries catching SBF:https://www.ccsbt.org/en/content/sbt-data. 	

Table 13. VLab 5 Input data sources

7.4. VLab availability

This VLab is available through Blue-Cloud gateway at

<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/globalfisheriesatlas>.

Part of the FAIR data and code generated by the Global Fisheries Atlas can also be found out of the VLab in widely used repositories. Some products of this VLab have been deployed on EDITO, e.g. RStudio instances or some of the global tuna atlas RShiny app is available in EDITO at <https://datalab.dive.edito.eu/catalog/all?search=tuna> (Global-tuna-atlas-shiny-app). Global Tuna Atlas datasets and code have also been assigned DOIs on Zenodo to better track their use and downloads (Figure 101): e.g. [All FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas products](#) (Level 0) and [Upper levels of processing](#). The main releases of the code that are published on Zenodo are directly synchronised with GitHub repositories (version DOIs are being assigned to the main releases of the repositories of the [FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas GitHub](#) page).

7.5. How to use the VLab

A self-paced training course for this VLab is available for free on the OceanTeacher Global Academy platform: <https://oceanexpert.org/event/4861>.

Once logged in, VLab members can access the VLab content in different ways depending on their needs and profiles:

- **Advanced users**
 - can launch RStudio server where they will find ready to go R projects directly cloned from the underlying GitHub organization and related repositories. This is a key asset to foster the reproducibility or customization of the work. These R projects include Shiny apps source code that is easy to run and the data generation workflow which can be executed from a single file.
 - can use the [GRSF API](#) or [SPARQL endpoint](#) to browse or extract specific content (Figure 100,101). GRSF API provides a formal way to access GRSF data (i.e. stocks and fishery data, as well as supplementary resources such as marine species, water areas, fishing gears, etc.). The API provides a collection of RESTful methods supporting the retrieval of resources using different combinations of parameters. Moreover, results can be delivered in various formats, such as JSON, CSV, XML, etc.
 - can query the content of the **Global Tuna Atlas relational database** (SQL, PostgreSQL / Postgis), indirectly through [one of the shiny applications](#) linked to the database.
- The **general public** / wider audience can browse the content of the VLab knowledge base and related datasets by using menu items, e.g.:
 - **“CKAN catalogue” menu item:** to discover and access GRSF content with CKAN catalogue sheets. By leveraging CKAN facilities, GRSF resources are displayed as distinct datasets, grouped based on their distinctive attributes (e.g. grouped per FAO major area, per species, etc., Figure 99).
 - **“Shiny apps” menu item:** provides a list of Shiny apps built on top of the Global Tuna Atlas (Figure 95, 96). Current apps demonstrates how atlas can easily be set up from FAIR fisheries data:
 - high resolution fisheries data complying with [Darwin Core](#) data format
 - lower resolution (gridded) fisheries data complying with [Coordinating Working Party on Fishery Statistics \(CWP\)](#) data format
 - **“viewer” menu item:** gives access to alternate Map viewers built on top of the Global Fisheries Atlas data or knowledge base. These web mapping apps demonstrate how other atlas can be set up from FAIR **Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)** compliant fisheries metadata and data:

- Fisheries Atlas map viewer: to spatially query, browse and display Global Tuna Atlas data catches (Figure 97). The same application is also in production out of the VLab on the [FIRMS Website](#) .

Figure 98. Fisheries Atlas shiny app for global gridded data, the example of Tuna Fisheries.

Figure 99. Fisheries Atlas shiny app to compare global gridded fisheries datasets with different levels of processing

Figure 100. GRSF map viewer to discover, query and display Global records of stocks and Fisheries.

zenodo Search records... Communities M Pour quitter le mode plein écran, appuyez de nouveau sur [Esc]

Published October 31, 2025 | Version 2025.2.0 Dataset Open

Global annual catches from tuna fisheries (1918-2023) (FIRMS level 0)

FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas Technical Working Group

Contributors

Hosting institution: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (UN-FAO)

Project members:

- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (UN-FAO)
- French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD)
- Commission for the Conservation of Southern Bluefin Tuna (CCSBT)
- Inter-American Tropical Tuna Commission (IATTC)
- International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT)
- Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC)
- Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission (WCPFC)

We constructed the most comprehensive dataset of nominal catches from global tuna fisheries by compiling and harmonizing public domain data from the five tuna Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (R-FMOs) for the period 1918-2023. Under the auspices of the Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System (FIRMS) of the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), we developed a systematic data flow process in collaboration with the R-FMO Secretariats. This process involved the implementation of a data exchange format adhering to the standards of the FAO Coordinating Working Party on Fishery Statistics (CWP), facilitating the seamless integration of data into the dataset.

Nominal catch data are expressed in live-weight equivalent (metric tonnes) and primarily represent the quantities of retained fish either landed or transhipped at sea and in ports. In recent years, data from fisheries in the Atlantic and Western-Central Pacific Oceans have partially included amounts of fish discarded dead. The data are stratified by year, fishing fleet, fishing gear, large spatial area, and taxon.

The dataset encompasses 50 medium- and large-sized pelagic species found in both neritic and oceanic habitats of the world's oceans. This includes 15 species of tunas, 10 species of billfish, 8 species of Spanish mackerels, 2 species of bonitos, and walrus. In 2023, the global catch for these species was estimated to exceed 6.4 million metric tonnes. Despite uncertainties and incomplete data due to under-reporting, the dataset also includes reported catches for 14 species of pelagic sharks and rays that may be either targeted or incidentally caught in tuna and tuna-like fisheries. The total reported catch of these elasmobranch species was approximately 154,000 metric tonnes in 2023.

The dataset serves as a benchmark for the monitoring and assessment of both artisanal and industrial fisheries from over 161 fishing fleets across 159 countries that have exploited tuna and tuna-like species for subsistence and commercial purposes over more than seven decades.

Methods (English)

Tuna Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (R-FMOs) are regional fishery bodies responsible for the conservation and management of tuna and tuna-like species, associated species, and their ecosystems across the Atlantic, Indian, and Pacific Oceans. R-FMOs routinely collate and consolidate fisheries data from their Contracting Parties to inform the scientific advice underpinning the management measures.

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Bluefin Tuna (CCSBT), the Inter-American Tropical

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Version	Date
Version 2025.2.0 10.5281/zenodo.17484424	Oct 31, 2025
Version 2025.1.1 10.5281/zenodo.15311770	Apr 30, 2025
Version 2025.1.0 10.5281/zenodo.15286474	Apr 26, 2025
Version 2024.1.0 10.5281/zenodo.11419529	Jun 1, 2024
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Figure 101. Zenodo DOI landing page displaying download options for a Global Fisheries Atlas data product.

Home / Records

Organisations	Search records...	
Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) (8488)	8,488 records found Order by: Relevance ▾	
Types	<p>Sepia hierredda - Sepia spp - Western Gulf of Guinea Assessment Unit</p> <p>Short Name: Cuttlefishes - Ghana GRSF Semantic Identifier: asfis:CVT;asfis:IAX+fao:34.3.4 Record URL: https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/GRSF/1a692423-1b56-3e6a-b343-c21ad41ac...</p> <p>CSV CSV</p>	
Fishing Unit (2959)	<p>Pecten fumatus - Bass Strait Central Zone Scallop Fishery Assessment Unit</p> <p>Short Name: Southern Australia scallop - Bass Strait GRSF Semantic Identifier: asfis:SSC+aus_cwf:BSCZSF Record URL:...</p>	
Traceability Unit (2911)	<p>Trisopterus esmarkii - Skagerrak and Kattegat (Division 27.3.a) - North Sea (...) Assessment Unit</p> <p>Short Name: Norway Pout - North Sea, Skagerrak and Kattegat GRSF Semantic Identifier: asfis:NOP+fao:27.3.a;fao:27.4 Record URL:...</p> <p>CSV CSV CSV CSV CSV CSV</p>	
Assessment Unit (2481)	<p>Panulirus homarus - Panulirus longipes - Panulirus ornatus - Panulirus versic... Marine Resource</p>	
Marine Resource (137)		
Groups		
GRSF (8488)		
FishSource (6552)		
RAM (3632)		
Catch (2985)		
Fishery (2959)		
Traceability Unit (2911)		
GRSF Traceability Flag (2685)		

Figure 102. The Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) knowledge base is made accessible with UI generated by a CKAN catalog.

Figure 103. The Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) knowledge base is made accessible with a Dashboard

Figure 104. The Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) knowledge base is made accessible with [a dedicated API](#)

7.6. Using other data sources

The R workflow which generates the Global Tuna Atlas can easily be reproduced or customized by using new input datasets as long as they can be harmonized to comply with similar data structures (implementation of the CWP data format for fisheries data). This harmonisation process can be managed by reusing and adapting the code used to transform the various data structures of the five tuna RFMOs datasets. Once CWP compliant, the data generation workflow can easily use the new data by adding a new corresponding line in the CSV file of the geoflow R package which orchestrates the different steps and sequence of actions executed by the workflow.

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- [2] Link to online CCP documentation: <https://ccp.cloud.d4science.org/docs/index.html>
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